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RENEWABLE ENERGY ENGINEERING PROGRAM

FINAL REPORT

PREDICTIVE MODEL DEVELOPMENT FOR HEAT LOAD IN BUILDINGS CONNECTED TO DISTRICT HEATING NETWORK

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Declaration

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Abstract

Characterizing and predicting the heat demand in buildings is vital for effective district heating operation and management. For this aim data driven models have played a major role in capturing important trends in energy consumption in order to predict future heating demand.

The purpose of this capstone is to investigate the heat load patterns in one building that is connected to district heating network (DH). In this context, we used a multi-step forecasting model that is able to accurately characterize and predict the heat demand. The model combines multiple variables such as: climatic variables (outdoor temperature, solar irradiation flux) and calendar data. The advantage of this model is the ability to be easily integrated into machines without special requirement and with a low computational cost.

Based on the experiment results, it has been shown that the proposed model is suitable for short term heat load forecasting. The best forecasting performance is achieved in winter term where the prediction values are from 4 to 20 % away from the targets, which are commonly seen as very good values.

Keywords: Data-driven model, District Heating, Short-term load forecasting, Energy efficiency

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Motivation

District Heating (DH) systems operated reliably over decades and provided a relevant share of energy to households across Europe. Currently, 12% of Europe's heating energy to buildings is delivered by District Heating Networks (DHNs), with more than 6000 systems serving around 60 million citizens. Moreover, some studies such as [1] estimated that market shares for District Heating can be increased to 30% in 2030 and 50% in 2050 by introducing renewables and waste heat in the supply. There are increasing variations in the system due to lower specific energy loads and intermittent renewable energy sources which raise the need for more accurate characterization and prediction of heat loads in buildings to ensure effective operation of these systems.

1.2 Project Context

The capstone project has been carried out in the context of Renewable Low Temperature District project (RELaTED). It is one of many projects that received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme [2].

The Horizon 2020 programme (figure 1) is a financial instrument that aims to secure Europe's global competitiveness and help to remove barriers to innovation and research. The programme is considered as the biggest Europe Research and Innovation programme with nearly €80 billion of funding [3].

Figure 1. Horizon 2020 programme logo (Source: Horizon, 2020)

The RELaTED Project (figure 2) is one of the projects that aim to reduce temperature levels in District Heating, with the integration of renewables at buildings and districts. This project provides innovative concepts that allow the incorporation of low-grade heat sources with minimal constraints. Also aim to reduce operational costs due to fewer heat losses. The RELaTED Project helps to increase the energy performance of heat generation plants. The proposed

approach follows the electrical smart grids strategy, where the energy generation is decentralized. This concept is demonstrated in four complementary operation environments: Denmark, Estonia, Serbia and Spain [\[4\]](#).

Figure 2. RElated Project logo (Source: related project, 2020)

Figure 3. RElated project locations (Source: related project, 2020)

1.3 Problem Statement

High fluctuation of renewable energy such as wind and photovoltaic (PV) can cause problems and hamper the stable operation of the electric power grid. That's why energy storage systems (ESS) play a major role in moderating this fluctuation. Indeed, ESS store the excess generated and make it accessible on demand. One of these systems that can act as an affordable thermal energy storage is District Heating (DH) networks.

To improve the control strategies of DH networks in combination with photovoltaics and wind energy production simulation-based studies need to be carried out. These studies not only include the production of PV and wind energy but also include the modelling of the heat demand in the district heating networks.

1.4 Purpose of the study

The main goal of this project, is to develop a predictive modelling approach for the heat load in buildings connected to DH systems. For doing so, we will use a black box model (BBM) which is a type of data driven models that use supervised machine learning algorithms. The main advantage of BBM is that it doesn't utilize the physical background of the building. Generally black box models depend on the quality of input data and allow to extract models from a large volume of data. Furthermore, choosing the right influential parameters when designing black box models play a major role in obtaining accurate result.

1.5 Research Questions

The main research questions that we are going to address in this capstone are:

Research Question 1: How to characterize the heat load in buildings connected to district heating system?

Research Question 2: How to accurately predict the heat demand in buildings connected to district heating system?

1.6 Approach and Boundaries of the Study

1.6.1 Research Approach

In the present study we wanted to determine the level to which we can characterize the heat load in buildings connected to district heating systems (DH) and inspect the extent to which we can predict the heat demand in these buildings. Therefore, we used quantitative design research approach. [\[5\]](#)

The quantitative research is divided into four main types: descriptive research, correlation research, causal-comparative & quasi-experimental research and finally the experimental research [\[6\]](#). The latter type will be selected as our quantitative design research approach. The experimental research or design of experiment (DOE) allows for multiple input factor to be manipulated and determine their effect on a desired response. In our capstone, it allows the weather along with social behavior factors to be manipulated in order to determine their effect on the heat load response variable. The DOE of the study provides answers to the following questions such as:

- What are the key factors in characterizing and predicting the heat demand in buildings connected to district heating systems?
- What settings would bring less variation in the heat load of district heating (DH)?
- At what settings the characterization and prediction of heat demand process deliver acceptable performance?

1.6.2 Scope of the study

The scope of the study is to develop a data driven model to characterize and estimate the dynamic relationships between the heat loads in buildings connected to district heating systems and other parameters such as weather variables (temperature and solar irradiation flux) along with calendar data. The calendar information evaluates the effect of social behavior of the occupant on the energy performance of the building.

The model is fed with hourly real data from smart heat meter in one building among 42 buildings connected to district heating in Tartu, Estonia. The meter delivers heat consumption data with one hour frequency.

1.6.3 Limitation of the Study

The datasets contain heat consumption hourly measurement of one year (2019) which results an uncertainty in identifying the heat load patterns. this small sample size was the one of the main limitations that we have face in the study.

Furthermore, the large variation in the quality of the smart heat meter data sample leads to limited information on the dataset. Indeed, the instability of the resolution of energy metering with regards to district heating measurement is caused by the accumulation of energy meter data to a given threshold in certain period of the year before the signals are logged. This threshold is too high compared to the energy consumption of the building (1 to 100 kWh) which affect the flexibility potential of the study.

Another limitation that affects the study, the lack of information of the building size and number of occupants. the aforementioned limitation makes it difficult to draw certain conclusion.

1.6.4 Delimitation of the Study

In this study, we decided to select one building among 42 buildings. The selection process was based on specific requirement such as the availability and quality of the data provided by the energy smart meter. Moreover, we decided to exclude some weather parameters including wind speed and relative humidity as these factors are not dominant compared to the outdoor temperature and more or less to the solar irradiation. Other physical parameters were excluded from the study, such as district heating flow temperature, district heating return temperature and volumetric flow rate.

1.6.5 Assumption of the Study

According to various studies [\[18\]](#) [\[19\]](#) the heat demand corresponding to building connected to district heating (DH) is affected by the weather and the human behavior consumption pattern represented by the calendar data. Therefore, we have assumed that the inclusion of these factors improves the heat demand forecasting accuracy.

1.7 Technical and Scientific Contribution

In this capstone we will investigate the heat load patterns in one building using multi-step forecasting model. In other word we will combine the Multivariate Linear Regression models (MLR) (to capture physical dependencies) with Segmented Auto Regressive models (S-ARX) (to deal with energy storage across data segments). We also add an Integration feature (to correct model inaccuracies), to obtain a robust and accurate regression model that we called S-ARX-MLR used in time series forecasting.

The main contribution of this capstone is the design of a new Segmented Multiple Linear Regression model that considers the recent history of past prediction values. The S-ARX-MLR is applied in a short-term heat load forecast with high temporal resolution (hourly and daily timestamp) for different buildings relying on weather and calendar information.

Furthermore, it will be valid for application over a variety of heat load profiles. Developing this new model will enable us to have accurate result of prediction with low calculation and processing cost.

1.8 Structure of the work

In the first chapter, we will introduce our research study. In particular, we will motivate our study and specify the arguments that show the importance of our project. Then we will describe the purpose of the study and the issues that we are going to address. Particularly, we will give more detail on how to construct our model.

In the second chapter, we will list the main concepts related to our study and take a look on other existing related studies.

In the third chapter, we will detail the methodology that is used to answer our research questions in this study.

In the fourth chapter, we will share the main findings of our study where the model will be evaluated for the purpose of characterizing and predicting the heat load.

In the fifth chapter, we will examine the limitation of the study. Moreover, we will discuss its industrial impact. Also, we will identify the threats to validity and the actions that we should take to tackle these threats.

Finally, we will we summarize the major findings and highlights future directions to where our study can be extended.

2. BACKGROUND and LITERATURE REVIEW

In this section we outline the prerequisite information needed for the study. First, we defined the main concepts including the topic of energy conservation in buildings, district heating systems and its model components related to end user profile. Then, we discussed existing related studies and compared it to our proposed research study.

2.1 Background

2.1.1 Energy conservation in buildings

Energy conservation in buildings has become a necessity for lessening the detrimental effects caused by the increase of urbanization worldwide where the number of buildings has escalated dramatically [7]. [8] define the energy conservation in buildings as a reduction of building energy consumption without reducing the thermal comfort.

In this context, unlocking the energy saving potential and promoting the technological solution help to boost the energy efficiency in buildings. To achieve this goal different strategies have been proposed including: refurbishment technologies such as solar shading and thermal insulation, improving the performance of HVAC equipment and promoting the integration of renewable energy sources.

In the next section, we will discuss another viable solution that could help to improve the energy efficiency in building is the district heating systems (DH).

2.1.2 District Heating System

A district heating is defined as underground infrastructure in which the thermal energy is provided to multiple building from a central energy plant [9]. The thermal energy is transmitted through highly insulated pipes including the steam and hot water. They are produced and transmitted twenty-four hours a day. The installation of district heating has numerous advantages, such as simplifying the building's maintenance and operation. Furthermore, it enables the fuel flexibility. Also connecting multiple building to district system helps to support the integration of cleaner options such as combined heat and power (CHP), biomass and other alternative sources [10]. Moreover, the district heating could use the surplus heat from industrial process.

Figure 4. Simplified conceptual diagram of district heating network
 (Source: boilerguide, 2022)

(Figure4) displays a simplified conceptual diagram of district heating network. The energy center represents the centralized power source in which the energy is generated. It could use several alternative energy sources including combined heat and power plant (CHP), boilers (biomass) or geothermal plant. The distribution network consists of insulated pipes with different diameters where the hot water is carried to the entire grid. Indeed, it is transported to the substation by the supply pipelines indicated by the red color in the figure. The water is back to the production side through the return pipeline by indicated by the blue color. For the consumer side which consists of housing, commercial and apartments as shown in the diagram, The heat energy is transferred through heat exchanger which include control valve actuator, flow meter and speed pump controls. The heat generated by the centralized power station is delivered to the entire grid and depends mainly on the temperature and flow rate [11]. The following equation formulate the heat energy at each substation.

Equation 1. Equation of the district heating net heat energy delivered to the grid

$$Q_{net} = Q_{loss} + \sum_{i=1}^n Q_{S_i}$$

Q_S is the heat demand in each substation S_i , Q_{loss} indicate the heat loss around the pipes. The component modelling of district heating system can be divided into two types: The first focuses on Q_{net} while the second consider the modelling of Q_S . In this context, the heat demand in each substation is affected by different parameters such as weather parameters and social behavior pattern. It can also be affected by the internal physical dynamics in district heating system. These parameters are classified into internal factors and external factors as illustrated below (see table 1)

Table 1. Factors that influence the heat load in district heating

External Factors		Internal Factors
Seasonal and Behavioral Factors	Weather Factors	
Hour of day	Outdoor temperature	Flow rate
Day of week	Solar radiation	Supply temperature
Month of year	Wind speed	Return temperature

2.1.3 End User Profile and Data Driven Modelling

The performance of the district heating network is mainly depended on the end user profile. The contribution of building's occupant could be performed by optimizing the end user side in term of heat demand, which can reduce the daily consumption of heat load. Therefore, the use of expensive sources of heat will be decreased significantly [12]. Also, in order to improve the efficiency of the district heating network and its optimization process, an accurate prediction of heat demand in smaller interval need to be modeled. The modelling process to characterize the heat demand profile required for the district heating system is carried out using different approaches [13].

One of these approaches is the data driven approach. As a matter of fact, it is the most well-known types of modelling in building energy estimation. Different types of data driven models can be performed. They are essentially divided into two groups: grey box models and black box models.

Grey box models

Depend on the knowledge of physical principles in the model domain. For example, the theoretical relation of heat transfer in buildings is taken into consideration therefore more complicated mathematical models need to be carry out.

Black box models

Black box models, which are the case of our study, don't use any type of physical background. In fact, these models are purely data driven that use supervised machine learning algorithms. The black box models have a set of mathematical principles that are similar to the techniques used in heat demand forecasting. The heat generation in District Heating (DH) networks has to be optimized. For that reason, these forecast models are used. Therefore, high

quality of input data is needed in this model in order to work in fast and efficient way. In addition, choosing the right parameters when designing a black box models play a major role in obtaining an accurate result.

2.2 Existing Related Studies

To ensure effective operation of DH networks, our study will focus on how to characterize and forecast the heating demand. For doing so, we use a data driven modelling approach based on black box models. In this regard, several studies were carried out to determine the model that predict the demand profile with precise and accuracy. One considerable technique used in predicting the demand profile of the users is the Predictive Time Series Methods. It comprises two well-known categories: Artificial intelligence and classical approaches.

2.2.1 Artificial Intelligence

A prominent approach of load prediction. It is dramatically used in energy system engineering [14]. The most common methods are ANN, FNN and SVM ([Appendix A](#)), for example in Hippert et al., 2001 [15] the study concludes that when taking into account the social parameters in local prediction could result a higher adaptability and lead to a high accuracy of the ANN model. Different approaches are tested to model Occupant Presence and Actions (OPA) in buildings. [16] represents a stochastic model that aims to capture the complexity of occupant social behavior by decoupling the presence of it and its actions. (Use of Windows, use of appliances...) In Page et al., 2007 [17] study, the author compared three principal machine learning algorithms K-nearest neighbors (KNN), Support Vector Machine (SVM) and Artificial Neural Network (ANN). Each model is coupled with a data source that includes different types of variables including environmental, Wi-Fi and fused data. The results showed that the ANN model combined with fused data has a good performance compared to other models, while the SVM model coupled with Wi-Fi data improve the model accuracy.

2.2.1 Classical Approaches

Classical approaches are introduced in several studies associated with Predictive Models. Such as, Autoregression (AR), Moving Average (MA), Autoregressive Moving Average (ARMA) and Seasonal Autoregressive Integrated Moving-Average (SARIMA) ([Appendix A](#)). One of the major advantages of these models is they do not require any prior knowledge of the building.

The study of Eguizabal et al., (2021) [18] proposed a data driven model based on present and recent history of weather data. This type of model, so called Autoregressive with exogenous variables, was optimized at 4-hour historical values. The training and testing process was performed against synthetic data a building energy simulation. The result of the study showed a stable forecasting model with an absolute error less than 4% knowing that these results were obtained for fixed thermostat values in a simulation environment. Another approach was delivered by Lumbreras et al., (2021) [19] in which a model was created based on supervised clustering methods combined with multiple climatic variable regression including global solar radiation and wind speed and direction. The model, so called Q-algorithm, forecast the heat load despite the characteristic and final use of building. The results of the models indicated an accurate heat demand prediction for more than 90% of the building connected to district heating systems. Moreover, the model showed an R-squared values 0.70 to 0.99 for daily data and 0.95 for hourly data. In Gross et al., (1987) [20], the author described the practical aspects for the development of ARMA models as the state of the art for short term heat load forecasting. In this context the model uses a linear combination between previous value of the load along with previous and current values of errors whereby the influences of weather deviation are described. This type of model is easy developed and updated to describe time correlated random phenomena. Fang et al., (2016) [21] used developed a seasonal autoregressive integrated moving average (SARIMA) with exogenous variables including weather factors and historical heat load consumption data. The model was tested on real life heat demand in the city of Espoo, Finland. The results indicated that the proposed model which used 168 hours of demand pattern with holiday has given a strong robustness in term of forecasting. The author suggested different area where we can deploy the model. It could be in the production planning of heat load and power (CHP) or individual buildings.

For the purpose of this capstone, we introduce a segmented Autoregressive model combined with a multiple linear regression (S-ARX model) that allows the existence of independent variables called exogenous variables. The S-ARX model includes disturbance dynamics within we can assure more flexibility when handling of the disturbance modelling. Ultimately, the model is capable of modelling the unknown with a minimum number of parameters, achieving substantial simplification of linear prediction and providing an effective linear model of stationary time series.

3. METHODOLOGY

In this section we describe our data driven approach. This approach is outlined in figure 5. It involves 5 major steps. (1) Data sources and data preprocessing: Where the sources and structure of our data is introduced. The data preprocessing procedure is applied, including duplicate removal, outlier detection and imputation process. (2) Load assessment and graphical exploration: in this step an initial analysis of the available dataset is performed with an identification of heat load patterns. (3) Model definition: The structure of the model is defined along with its general equation. (4) Model calibration: In our study the calibration process has three main tasks. First, the segmentation of the dataset. Second, the application of statistical significance along with feature selection method. And finally, the application of model optimization. (5) Result process and validation: This step includes the selection of model based on different evaluation metrics. Additionally, the model is evaluated in term of seasonal performance variation.

Figure 5. General Methodology of the study

3.1 Data Sources and Data Preprocessing

3.1.1 Implementation

The analysis and algorithms were implemented using Python, a high level and object-oriented programming language that is useful for rapid application development. It supports several modules and packages. Different libraries were utilized in this study:

- Pandas: Open-source manipulation tool for data analysis.
- Scikit learn: Efficient tool used for predictive data analysis.
- NumPy: Offers several comprehensive mathematical concepts.
- Matplotlib and Seaborn: a data visualization tool that provide informative statistical graphics.

The implementation of the codes was done on an interactive environment called Collaboratory notebook provided by Google, it allows to execute python in our browser with configuration required. The content of the study with the implemented codes is available on GitHub.

3.1.2 Data Sources and Structure

The sources of our data came from two locations: district heating substations and weather station. The sub-network of the district heating covers 42 substations (buildings), located in Tartu (Estonia). The datasets were collected from each substation. We attached, in each building, an energy smart meter ([Kamstrup](#)) [22] that measures constantly different variables represented in the heat load (KW), volumetric flow rate(m³/h), and five different supply and return temperatures(°C). The device sends the real time measured data to [GREN](#), the operator responsible for the district heating [23].

Data taken from the weather station is located in the university of Tartu (Estonia) and have 15-minute frequency basis [24]. The dataset related to the weather station comprise the outdoor temperature, wind speed(m/s), wind direction, irradiation flux(W/m²) and calendar data. From the heat meter original dataset, we have chosen the heat load variables and discarded the other parameter as it will not be included in our study.

From the weather station dataset, we have selected the outdoor temperature and the solar irradiation since it has been proven in different studies the high correlation between these two parameters with the heat load compared to other parameters (wind speed, humidity etc.)

Table 2. Smart energy meter variables and weather variables. (The variables included in our study are highlighted)

	Variables	Unit
Smart Energy Meter Variables	Heat Load per Hour	KW
	Volumetric Flow Rate	m ³ /h
	Supply Temperatures	°C
	Return Temperatures	°C
Weather Variables	Ambient Temperature	°C
	Wind Direction	-
	Wind Speed	m/s
	Solar Irradiation Flux	W/m ²

Before doing the coupling process, where the weather data and heat load are combined into a single dataset, we resample the weather data from 15 min to hour frequency. Thus, we obtain 7680 rows indicating every hour in the year.

Table 3. The dataset in which the heat load and weather data are combined

	READ_DATE	Day	Day_month	Month	Year	Hour	Hour_day	Week_Day	Temperature	Irradiation.flux	POWER1
0	2019-01-01 00:00:00	1	1	1	2019	1	0	TUE	-1.15	4.21	71.1
1	2019-01-01 01:00:00	1	1	1	2019	2	1	TUE	-0.94	4.23	69.3
2	2019-01-01 02:00:00	1	1	1	2019	3	2	TUE	-0.80	4.13	69.2
3	2019-01-01 03:00:00	1	1	1	2019	4	3	TUE	-0.60	4.04	70.5
4	2019-01-01 04:00:00	1	1	1	2019	5	4	TUE	-0.10	4.93	70.2
...
8755	2019-12-31 19:00:00	365	31	12	2019	8756	19	TUE	0.52	4.30	67.6
8756	2019-12-31 20:00:00	365	31	12	2019	8757	20	TUE	-0.72	3.92	69.6
8757	2019-12-31 21:00:00	365	31	12	2019	8758	21	TUE	-1.32	4.14	69.9
8758	2019-12-31 22:00:00	365	31	12	2019	8759	22	TUE	-1.69	4.01	68.1
8759	2019-12-31 23:00:00	365	31	12	2019	8760	23	TUE	-1.69	4.11	73.8

3.1.3 Selection of Buildings

The District Heating (DH) network comprise 42 substations (buildings). The table 4. below indicates the type of buildings connected to the district heating network.

Table 4. The building connected to district heating network

Type of Buildings	Number of Buildings
Offices	1
Commercial Buildings	1
Private House	7
Educational Buildings	8
Residential apartments	25

As can be seen from the (Fig. 6), We have noticed a range of different heat load profiles among the 42 buildings, this could be explained by the different final use of buildings. In this perspective the diverse patterns of heat load are derived from the sensitivity, dynamic nature and socio-cultural attitude of the occupant behavior.

Figure 6. Example of two different hourly heat load (kWh) profiles: (a) building 10051, (b) building 10298

One building has been selected among the 42 buildings connected to the district heating sub-network in Tartu, it has been given an ID with serial number to preserve the privacy of the user. The selected building:

Building 1: Meter ID 10295

The selection process is based on specific requirements, such as selecting the building dataset which has a full year data with at least more than 8000 valid data points leading to a clear shape of the hourly heat load.

Figure 7. Hourly heat load in building 10259 (before data cleaning)

Figure 8. Hourly heat load vs outdoor temperature in building 10259 (before data cleaning)

Fig 7. demonstrates the hourly heat load with times in hours. One can see that the decrease in heat load does not decline totally in the summer period (between 4000 hours to 6000 hours). A reason for this pattern is that the total heat consumption does not include only the space heating but also includes the hot water production which is known to have no dependence on climatic variables, it rather depends on the random nature of specific user behavior according to [18].

Fig 8. shows the hourly heat load with outdoor temperature. We can see the decrease in the heat load is followed by a growth in terms of outdoor temperature. This increase indicates the large correlation between weather variable and heating demand.

3.1.4 Removing Duplicates

The step of removing duplicates is when we identify and remove instances where there is more than one record of a single observation. Duplicates is considered as one of the most common issues in data preprocessing, which could occur as a result of customer input error when importing and exporting errors from the smart meter. We perform this step to avoid the disproportionate weight during training that leads to the decrease of model performance. Moreover, it violates the split of data (Training & testing) and generate a biased model. As illustrated in table 5. below, 9023 records have been found which indicate the existence of duplicate entries. Our dataset must have about 8760 observation which correspond to the number of hours per year. (Table 6)

Table 5. Original dataset before executing the removing duplicate process (with 9023 observation)

Unnamed: 0	METERID	ENERGY	VOLUME	HOURS	POWER1	FLOW	FLOW_TEMP	RETURN_TEMP	HOT_WATER	SEC_FLOW	SEC_RETURN	READ_DATE	
0	NaN	10259	11.050	245.49	4549	23.2	553	73.82	37.97	55.99	41.21	31.75	2019-01-01 00:00:00
1	NaN	10259	11.072	245.99	4550	18.4	435	73.72	36.34	55.03	40.96	31.87	2019-01-01 01:00:00
2	NaN	10259	11.091	246.44	4551	18.9	437	74.02	36.61	55.25	41.21	31.87	2019-01-01 02:00:00
3	NaN	10259	11.112	246.92	4552	21.4	506	74.15	37.58	55.44	41.34	31.75	2019-01-01 03:00:00
4	NaN	10259	11.135	247.43	4553	30.9	660	73.95	33.73	55.14	41.09	31.81	2019-01-01 04:00:00
...
9018	NaN	10259	128.224	3304.09	13304	18.1	523	66.21	36.57	53.93	39.52	30.62	2019-12-31 19:00:00
9019	NaN	10259	128.242	3304.65	13305	17.9	528	66.32	37.02	54.00	39.33	30.68	2019-12-31 20:00:00
9020	NaN	10259	128.264	3305.25	13306	22.4	650	66.38	37.96	53.72	40.15	30.68	2019-12-31 21:00:00
9021	NaN	10259	128.283	3305.83	13307	17.5	538	66.39	38.12	54.43	40.84	31.00	2019-12-31 22:00:00
9022	NaN	10259	128.305	3306.49	13308	23.0	680	66.23	35.66	53.98	41.21	31.25	2019-12-31 23:00:00

9023 rows x 13 columns

Table 6. Original dataset after executing the removing duplicate process (with 8760 observation)

Unnamed: 0	METERID	ENERGY	VOLUME	HOURS	POWER1	FLOW	FLOW_TEMP	RETURN_TEMP	HOT_WATER	SEC_FLOW	SEC_RETURN	READ_DATE	
0	NaN	10259	11.050	245.49	4549	23.2	553	73.82	37.97	55.99	41.21	31.75	2019-01-01 00:00:00
1	NaN	10259	11.072	245.99	4550	18.4	435	73.72	36.34	55.03	40.96	31.87	2019-01-01 01:00:00
2	NaN	10259	11.091	246.44	4551	18.9	437	74.02	36.61	55.25	41.21	31.87	2019-01-01 02:00:00
3	NaN	10259	11.112	246.92	4552	21.4	506	74.15	37.58	55.44	41.34	31.75	2019-01-01 03:00:00
4	NaN	10259	11.135	247.43	4553	30.9	660	73.95	33.73	55.14	41.09	31.81	2019-01-01 04:00:00
...
8755	NaN	10259	128.224	3304.09	13304	18.1	523	66.21	36.57	53.93	39.52	30.62	2019-12-31 19:00:00
8756	NaN	10259	128.242	3304.65	13305	17.9	528	66.32	37.02	54.00	39.33	30.68	2019-12-31 20:00:00
8757	NaN	10259	128.264	3305.25	13306	22.4	650	66.38	37.96	53.72	40.15	30.68	2019-12-31 21:00:00
8758	NaN	10259	128.283	3305.83	13307	17.5	538	66.39	38.12	54.43	40.84	31.00	2019-12-31 22:00:00
8759	NaN	10259	128.305	3306.49	13308	23.0	680	66.23	35.66	53.98	41.21	31.25	2019-12-31 23:00:00

8760 rows x 13 columns

3.1.5 Outlier Identification and Imputation process

The outlier identification is important step since it indicates whether we have a bad data resulted from experiment that may have not run-in proper way. In general, the outlying values should be deleted. In this study the outlier detection process is applied on the heat load since it is the target variable to be predicted. Identification of outliers requires the normality assumption of our data, where the observations follow an approximately normal distribution. For this reason, the normal probability plot and histogram have been used as methods to test for normality and identifying potential outliers.

Figure 9. Histogram and normal probability plot used for the normality test: (a) frequency (count) vs heat load, (b) sample quantiles (actual data) vs theoretical quantiles (z-score)

In the sub figure (a) we can see a large deviation from the normal distribution curve. In the normal probability plot (b) the line is largely skewed to the left. As a consequence, we can say that we do not have a normally distributed data.

With the aim of dealing with outliers and reading errors, we propose the interquartile range method (IQR). The aforementioned method measures the spread of our data and represent the range for the middle of the samples. The figure below shows the normal distribution cure where:

Q1: the first quartile where 25 % of the data lie between the minimum value and Q1.

Q3: the third quartile where 75% of the data lie between the minimum value and Q3.

Figure 10. The normal distribution bell curve (source: CDC 2012)

The IQR is found by subtracting Q1 from Q3 as shown in the equation:

Equation 2. IQR formula (source: CDC 2012)

$$IQR = Q3 - Q1$$

Using the Interquartile range (IQR), we define a range at which any data point lying outside this range is considered as potential outlier. The range is composed of two bounds.

Equation 3. Lower and upper bound formula (source: CDC 2012)

$$\text{Lower bound: } (Q1 - 1.5 * IQR)$$

$$\text{Upper bound: } (Q3 + 1.5 * IQR)$$

All observation lying above the third quartile + 1.5*IQR and lying below the first quartile - 1.5*IQR is considered as outliers. In our case we have replaced the 1.5 constant with 1 in order to make it less sensitive to the abnormal values. Hence, a total of 4 % of probability of lying in the outlier zone were identified. Conversely, we cannot carry out this process directly since our dataset is not randomly distributed due to climatic reasons. As a result, we have performed a preliminary step in which we have divided the data into 21 subsets of temperature, each temperature subset is marked at an interval of 2.5 °C. We have taken one of the subsets (as shown in table 7. below) as an example to show how did we apply the outlier detection process using the IQR method. In this context we have selected a range of data lying between 0°C and 2.5°C (representing a subset) in order to make the normality assumption valid.

Table 7. Example of subset where a range of temperature between 0°C and 2.5°C are selected from the original dataset to validate the normality assumption and apply the outlier detection process

	READ_DATE	Day	Day_month	Month	Year	Hour	Hour_day	Week_Day	Temperature	Irradiation.flux	POWER1
6	2019-01-01 06:00:00	1	1	1	2019	7	6	TUE	0.14	4.70	17.7
7	2019-01-01 07:00:00	1	1	1	2019	8	7	TUE	0.39	4.40	18.6
8	2019-01-01 08:00:00	1	1	1	2019	9	8	TUE	0.51	4.72	18.5
9	2019-01-01 09:00:00	1	1	1	2019	10	9	TUE	0.68	8.77	17.5
10	2019-01-01 10:00:00	1	1	1	2019	11	10	TUE	1.01	22.71	19.1
...
8751	2019-12-31 15:00:00	365	31	12	2019	8752	15	TUE	0.52	3.90	16.6
8752	2019-12-31 16:00:00	365	31	12	2019	8753	16	TUE	0.62	3.97	19.6
8753	2019-12-31 17:00:00	365	31	12	2019	8754	17	TUE	0.67	3.59	21.3
8754	2019-12-31 18:00:00	365	31	12	2019	8755	18	TUE	0.57	4.32	18.7
8755	2019-12-31 19:00:00	365	31	12	2019	8756	19	TUE	0.52	4.30	18.1

1160 rows × 11 columns

Figure 11. Histogram (a) and normal probability plot (b) before applying the IQR method to the data subset

Figure 12. Histogram (a) and normal probability plot (b) after applying the IQR method to the data subset

As presented in sub-figures (b) above, the skewness (in fig 11) is removed and replaced with a straight diagonal line (fig 12), meaning that we have normally distributed our data. The same goes for the sub figures (a) where the shape of the bell curve is no longer deviated (fig 11) and become conformed with the histogram (fig 12)

In order to fill the missing value resulted from the outlier removal, an imputation process have been executed by filling the heat load missing value by the average from the same hour taken from the rest of the data. Knowing that this process has been done for every subset of temperature.

3.2 Load Assessment & Graphic Exploration

Plotting time series values for the selected building dataset allow to identify different patterns such as trends and seasonality. Moreover, it enables many features of the data. In particular, we can highlight the changes over time and recognize unusual observations.

In this section we have performed the load assessment process in two different periods: full year and winter term to perceive if there are any hidden patterns.

3.2.1 Full Year & Winter Term

The decrease in the heat load (fig 13) was followed by a growth in terms of outdoor temperature. This increase indicates the strong correlation between weather variable and heating demand. Part of the heating demand is dedicated to domestic hot water consumption (DHW) which is illustrated by the roughly horizontal profile against the weather data. Indeed, the hot water consumption shows little to no dependence on weather variable and seasonal variation.

Also, a large correlation between heat load and temperature can be detected (fig 14). In particular, at lower temperature (between -5 to -20°C) we can see a considerable variability where the non-stability of the heat load demand is caused by the decrease in temperature. On the other hand, the rising temperature leads to a stable profile. This could be explained by the consumer behavior randomness in term of heat energy consumption during the extreme low temperature.

Figure 13. Hourly heat load vs outdoor temperature in building 10259

Figure 14. Hourly heat load vs outdoor temperature in building 10259 (winter term)

The decrease in heat load (fig 15) does not decline totally in the summer period (between 4000 hours to 6000 hours). One reason of this pattern is that the total heat consumption does not include only the space heating but also includes the hot water production which is known to have no dependence on climatic variables, it rather depends on the random nature of specific user behavior.

Figure 15. Hourly heat load in building 10259

For the winter term as presented in fig 16, an increase centered at the beginning of January (0 to 250 hours) can be noticed, followed by a very accentuated demand peak starting from the mid of January (500 to 750 hours).

The plot in fig 17 below shows a remarkable decline in heat load on November (7400 to 7800 hours), subsequently it increases and remain stable at the level of 20 to 30 kWh.

Figure 16. Hourly heat load in building 10259 (January to March)

Figure 17. Hourly heat load in building 10259 (November to December)

Annual Seasonality

In fig 18 below, the graph represents the hourly heat load distribution by month. A sharp decrease is detected in median heat load in which the line continues to fall to reach the lowest level from July to August and rise again in the fall term (October to November). From this observation we can confirm that we have a clear annual seasonality.

During winter term (fig 19 below) January represents the highest month in term of energy consumption unlike November which has the lowest hourly heat load comparing to other months.

Figure 18. Hourly heat load distribution by month

Figure 19. Hourly heat load distribution by month (winter term)

Weekly Seasonality

Figure 20. Hourly heat load distribution by weekday

Figure 21. Hourly heat load distribution by weekday (winter term)

Apart from the slight increase on Thursday as can be seen in fig 20 above. The hourly heat load on the other days remains stable with no significant changes in the median heat load along the weekday for both full year and winter term (fig 20 and fig 21)

Daily Seasonality

Figure 22. Hourly heat load distribution by time of the day

Figure 23. Hourly heat load distribution by time of the day (winter term)

In fig 22 above, we plot the hourly heat load distribution by time of the day. We observe a sharp decrease in median heat load between 7 to 10 am. This decrease is continued little by little before stabilizing between 18:00 and 23:00.

For the winter term (Fig 23.), we see a small decrease in the median line of the heat load from 3:00 to 5:00. This could be explained by the night setback where a reduction heat load occurred by the district heating operator.

In general, the night setback in district heating is considered as a control strategy to enable the control of the demand peak.

Figure 24. Hourly heat load distribution by time of the day for each weekday

Figure 25. Hourly heat load distribution by time of the day for each weekday (winter term)

For both fig 24. and fig 25. which represent the hourly heat load distribution by the time of the day for each weekday in full year and winter term respectively, we observe that a sharp decrease of heat load occurred from 5:00 to 15:00. In addition, we can see an increase

centered between 20:00 and 23:00. From 5:00 to 8:00 a very accentuated demand peak spotted. As evidenced from both figures, All the days have similar patterns with clear shape on Tuesday.

Holidays and non-holiday days

The two-violin plot (fig 26 below) represent the heat load distribution for the holidays and non-holiday days. As it might be seen, the holiday heat load distribution is poorly concentrated in the median compared to the non-holiday day. Moreover, a high upper interquartile range in the non-holiday days is noticed. Therefore, we could say that the holiday days tend to have lower heat load demand.

Figure 26. Heat load distribution between holiday and non-holiday

Figure 27. Autocorrelation plot

Figure 28. Partial autocorrelation plot

Also, a significant autocorrelation as demonstrated in both autocorrelation and partial autocorrelation plots. The clear association between one hour's heat load demand and previous hour indicates that autoregressive models [32] can work well in our dataset.

3.3 Model Definition

The proposed model uses a Segmented Autoregressive model with exogenous variables based on the multiple linear regression approach (S-ARX-MLR model). It is expected to forecast short-term heat load with hourly load data. The model handles each hour of the week separately and develops an individual model with calibrated parameters for each segment. The linear regression function is performed in order to identify the ARX coefficients, where the heat load output value is considered in previous timesteps. The model components are presented in the following equation:

Equation 4. S-ARX-MLR Model Structure

$$L_i = c + \sum(a_{na} \times L_{i-na}) + \sum(b_{nb} \times T_{i-nb}) + \sum(c_{nc} \times I_{i-nc}) + \sum(e_{ne} \times bool_CD) + w_i$$

Where a_{na} are the autoregressive parameter, b_{nb} , c_{nc} are the exogenous parameters, and e_{ne} are the parameter related to calendar data. The L_i refers to the heat load at time t (hours), L_{i-na} , T_{i-nb} and I_{i-nc} represent the present and lagged heat load, temperature and irradiation flux variables respectively. The calendar data are symbolized as $bool_CD$ which represent each hour of the week separately. Finally, w_i is identified as white noise parameter with a constant term c as well.

As a first approach, the S-ARX model was built using multiple linear regression method. The linear regression allows to predict the outcome of dependent variable. Additionally, it enables

the relative contribution of each independent variable in the total variance and allow to uncover the model variation. To do so, up to 231 input variables are considered in the modelling process in which 12 lagged dependent value representing the heat load regressors, 24 lagged explanatory variables related to temperature and irradiation flux along with their present values. Furthermore, we include 168 seasonal dummy variables which accounts for the number of hours for the full week separately along with the hours of holidays.

The aforementioned model is defined as S-ARX_LX_TY_IZ. Where X, Y and Z indicate the number of lagged values for the heat load, temperature and irradiation flux respectively. As an example, the following equation presents the formulation associated with our general model S_ARX_L12_T24_I24.

Equation 5. The formulation associated to the general model

$$L_i = c + \sum(a_{12} \times L_{i-12}) + \sum(b_{24} \times T_{i-24}) + \sum(c_{24} \times I_{i-24}) + \sum(e_{168} \times bool_CD) + w_i$$

Figure 29. Model Structure with input parameters

3.4 Model Calibration

The dataset was split into training and testing sets. The splitting process was performed in a way that the learning data and testing data coincide with all different heat consumption patterns with the respect to the season of the year. The training data have been defined containing odd days whereas the testing set have been defined containing even days.

The odd days were used to perform the heat load characterization and profiling along with the calibration process. In contrast the even days were used to measure and verify the model's performance to predict the heat demand.

As illustrated in the diagram below (fig 30) the data will be limited only to winter term (December to February) and shoulder season (March - May + Sep - Nov). The shoulder term is a period in the year that occurs between the peak and off-peak season where the outdoor temperature is close enough to building's internal temperature. The summer term will be excluded in this study to avoid the excessive relevance of period that have low heat load. Furthermore, the workdays and weekends were separated in order to remove the intraweek seasonality.

Figure 30. Data segmentation process

Feature Selection with Variance Thresholding

Each of the four models were fitted to the ordinary least square regression (OLS) [30]. Thereafter a feature selection using variance threshold was conducted. In this context, only the attributes that have significant effect on the model's output have been selected.

The selection procedure was based on p-value threshold in which the entry criterion was set to a value less than 0.05. To explain the variance in heat load outcome, the features were ranked by their individual ability, this means that each predictor that have a p-value greater 0.05 is excluded from the model.

The models were refitted several times until no feature have a p-value greater than 0.05. The aforementioned process is exemplified by the diagram below (fig 31), in which we choose the model of workdays data in winter term as an example to perform the feature selection method.

Figure 31. Example of least square estimation with feature selection method for workdays model of winter term

Data Scenarios and Model Optimization

In order to evaluate the effect of including various types of input variables for heat load prediction. Three different types of data (called "data scenarios") are demonstrated "lagged heat load", "lagged weather data" and "calendar data". Table 8 displays the data used in each scenario.

Table 8. Models with different data scenarios. Each of them has different input parameters. Adding the variables is based on an iterative process using forward selection method.

Models with different data scenarios	Power-lag1 to Power-lag12	Variables to enter to the models				
		Temperature-lag0	Temperature-lag1 to Temperature-lag24	Irradiation-flux-lag0	Irradiation-flux-lag1 to Irradiation-flux-lag24	Calendar Data
Model with lagged heat load data	✓					
Model with lagged weather data (Temperature)	✓	✓	✓			

Model with lagged weather data (Irradiation flux)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Model with calendar data	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

In each model, optimal input parameters are selected in order to achieve the best performance of prediction accuracy of heat load. Adding variables were based on an iterative process that used forward selection [31] where every addition of input variables to the model is evaluated using different evaluation metrics such as the Akaike information criterion (AIC), Bayesian information criterion (BIC) and Adjusted R-squared.

The Akaike information criterion (AIC) is used to estimate the likelihood of a model to predict the future value. Additionally, it enables the comparison of different input parameters.

In general, the model that have minimum value of AIC is considered the best one among other models. We define this metric as:

Equation 6. Akaike information criterion formula (source: Statistics How To, 2023)

$$AIC = N \log\left(\frac{SSE}{N}\right) + 2(k + 2)$$

Where N is the number of observation (number of hours in our case study), k is the number of predictors and the *SSE* which represents the sum of squares of errors.

Other criteria to select the parameters for heat load prediction, is the Bayesian information criterion (BIC). It is similar to the AIC. However, it penalizes the number of predictors more heavily than the AIC. It is defined as follows:

Equation 7. Bayesian information criterion formula (source: Statistics How To, 2023)

$$BIC = N \log\left(\frac{SSE}{N}\right) + (k + 2)\log(N)$$

Unlike the conventional R-squared metric, the adjusted R-squared does not always increase with each added predictor. Hence, it could help us to select and optimize the input parameters in the model. The larger value of adjusted R-squared we have the better the model will be in term of prediction accuracy. The formula of this metric is defined below as the following equation:

Equation 8. Adjusted R-squared formula(source: Statistics How To, 2023)

$$\bar{R}^2 = 1 - (1 - R^2) \frac{N - 1}{N - k - 1}$$

The aforementioned process is exemplified in the diagram of fig 32. below.

Figure 32. Diagram of different models of workdays in winter term with various type of data called data scenarios. Each model comprised of optimal input parameters

3.5 Result Process & Validation

The results process and validation were measured using two different aspects:

First using the training data, the accuracy of models was measured in order to characterize the heat load. In this context we checked the goodness of fit for each model with the calculation of R-squared value and F-statistic. The R-squared indicate the heat load variation in the response variable.

Equation 9. R-squared formula (source: Statistics How To, 2023)

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\text{sum squared regression (SSR)}}{\text{total sum of squares (SST)}}$$

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{\sum (y_i - \bar{y}_i)^2}$$

SSR represents the sum of the residuals squared and SSE represents the total sum of squares which is the sum of distance where the data is away from the mean. The residual values are denoted by \hat{y}_i and the mean of the response variable is denoted by \bar{y}_i .

Moreover, the F-statistic value has been used in order to determine the overall significance of the regression models. It can be calculated using the following formula.

Equation 10. F-statistic formula (source: Statistics How To, 2023)

$$F \text{ statistic} = \frac{MSR}{MSE}$$

$$MSR = \frac{SSR}{DF_{SSR}}$$

$$MSE = \frac{SSE}{DF_{SSE}}$$

The F-statistic formula is defined by the division of mean sum of squares regression, denoted by *MSR*, by the mean sum of squares error (*MSE*). The computation of *MSR* is performed by dividing the sum of squares regression (*SSR*) by the regression model degree of freedom (DF_{SSR}). Similar formula is applied to the MSE, where the sum of squares error (SSE) is divided by the degree of freedom for error (DF_{SSE}).

Afterward the F-statistic value is compared to the F- critical value (0.05 in our study case), if F-statistic greater than F-critical value we can say there is significance between the independent variables and the response variable.

Furthermore, visual inspection of residual analysis has been conducted. Several plots were represented to check if our assumption were reasonable and whether the choice of the models was appropriate or not. Specifically, these plots comprise the Actual vs Predicted data graphs (indicate the level accuracy of the models), Residual vs Predicted data graphs (used to detect the non-linearity or unequal error variance in the models) and the normal Quantile - Quantile plot (Q-Q plot) (to assess the data skewness and judge the normality distribution of the residual points.)

The second aspect of result process and validation was conducted based on model selection and testing, with the purpose of having accurate models to predict the heat load. Within this context, the models that performs well on previously unseen data is considered as good forecasting model.

The testing set was used to estimate the generalization performance of the forecasts. Different models with their data scenario have been scored according to hourly mean absolute error (MAE) and root mean square error (RMSE).

Equation 11. Root mean square error formula (source: Statistics How To, 2023)

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_t (\hat{P}_t - P_t)^2}$$

Where N is number of hours and \hat{P}_t is the foretasted heat load. In general, the RMSE measures the errors of the model. Specifically, it estimates the spread of prediction errors from the regression line.

Equation 12. Mean absolute error formula (source: Statistics How To, 2023)

$$MAE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_t |\hat{P}_t - P_t|$$

Compared to the RMSE, the mean absolute error (MAE) is less sensitive to large errors. Therefore, the difference between the predicted errors and actual values were computed. The low values of RMSE and MAE indicate the good accuracy of the model.

Another forecast error metric has been used in addition to RMSE and MAE. The mean absolute percentage error (MAPE). this metric was applied to the analysis of seasonal performance variation whereby the performance of the models was evaluated throughout the year. On top of that it can facilitate the comparison of different predictive models between different district heating systems.

Equation 13. Mean absolute percentage error formula (source: Statistics How To, 2023)

$$MAPE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_t \left| \frac{\hat{P}_t - P_t}{P_t} \right|$$

The MAPE is represented by the sum of individual errors divided by each period separately. It describes the average of the percentage errors.

4. RESULTS AND FINDINGS

In the present study, one building has been selected among buildings connected to district heating networks. In this section, the results were obtained from the application of the models.

In the first part we have explained the overall relationship between predictors and outcome variable. In this context the best estimates for the coefficient to fit the model have been assessed. Moreover, a summary statistic table was presented in order to evaluate how the regression models fits the data. As regards to the graphical residual analysis, several plots were represented to check if our assumption were reasonable and whether the choice of model were appropriate or not.

In the second part, we have optimized the models' parameters for prediction purpose. To accomplish that, several steps were performed in order to evaluate the forecast accuracy of the models. First the optimal lagged heat load variables along with the temperature and irradiation flux lagged values, were selected during a calibration process in order to choose the optimal models in term of prediction accuracy. Moreover, the significant calendar data are added in order to improve these models.

In the last part, we have tested the forecasting performance of each model with all the possible data scenarios. The models with best data scenario were selected and followed by an analysis of the seasonal performance variations.

4.1 Model Evaluation To characterize The Heat Load

4.1.1 Least Squares Estimation and Statistical Significance

Table 9. Number of predictor variables proposed for the models

Season	Week	Heat Load Predictor Variables	Temperature Predictor Variables	Irradiation Flux Predictor Variables	Hours of the Week Dummy Variables
Winter Models	Workdays Model	12	25	25	169
	Weekends Model	12	25	25	169
Shoulder Models	Workdays Model	12	25	25	169
	Weekends Model	12	25	25	169

Up to 12 lagged heat load predictor variables, are proposed for each model which represent 12 hour of heat load historical data. These values are coupled with 25 weather variables for the temperature and irradiation flux each. The weather variables contain one present value (representing the present hour) and 24 lagged values (representing the 24 previous hours). In addition, 169 of dummy variables are suggested as an input for the models. They refer to the number of hours of the full week.

Table 10. Regression models coefficients and P-value of significant variables (winter term)

Winter					
Workdays			Weekends		
Predictor variables	Coefficients	P-value	Predictor variables	Coefficients	P-value
POWER1_lag1	0.1294	0.000	POWER1_lag1	0.1891	0.001
POWER1_lag2	0.0948	0.006	POWER1_lag2	0.0567	0.301
POWER1_lag3	0.0770	0.022	POWER1_lag3	0.1935	0.000
POWER1_lag12	0.1561	0.023	Temperature_lag0	-0.5116	0.000
Temperature_lag0	-1.0102	0.000	Irradiation.flux_lag0	0.0237	0.015
Temperature_lag1	0.9428	0.053	Irradiation.flux_lag1	-0.0421	0.010
Temperature_lag2	-0.3335	0.516	Irradiation.flux_lag2	0.0266	0.006
Temperature_lag3	-0.9481	0.047	Irradiation.flux_lag11	0.0207	0.001
Temperature_lag4	0.7633	0.002	Irradiation.flux_lag12	-0.0204	0.001
Tuesday 1h	-2.1551	0.012	Saturday 10h	3.8600	0.000
Friday 16h	2.2787	0.014	Sunday 10h	2.4852	0.013
Monday 8h	2.5612	0.006			

Table 11. Regression models coefficients and P-value of significant variables (shoulder months)

Shoulder					
Workdays			Weekends		
Predictor variables	Coefficients	P-value	Predictor variables	Coefficients	P-value
POWER1_lag1	0.2897	0.000	POWER1_lag1	0.2603	0.000
POWER1_lag2	0.2338	0.000	POWER1_lag2	0.2043	0.000
Temperature_lag0	-0.6507	0.000	POWER1_lag3	0.1154	0.003
Temperature_lag1	0.2596	0.012	Temperature_lag0	-0.3119	0.000
Temperature_lag24	-0.0401	0.029	Temperature_lag24	-0.0700	0.038
Irradiation.flux_lag1	-0.0062	0.000	Irradiation.flux_lag4	0.0033	0.000
Irradiation.flux_lag2	0.0042	0.010	Irradiation.flux_lag24	-0.0017	0.003
Irradiation.flux_lag3	7.809e-05	0.962	Saturday 22h	1.3799	0.027
Irradiation.flux_lag4	-0.0020	0.222	Sunday 10h	1.2742	0.032
Irradiation.flux_lag5	0.0059	0.000	Sunday 18h	1.2186	0.038
Irradiation.flux_lag6	-0.0029	0.005	Sunday 22h	1.2110	0.037

Thursday 2h	-1.3630	0.025			
Friday 10h	-1.6718	0.003			
Friday 21h	1.1456	0.044			
Monday 0h	-1.3003	0.032			
Monday 1h	-1.2724	0.037			
Monday 8h	1.5540	0.011			

As can be seen from (table.10 ,11) the p-value of the predictor variables, in both winter and shoulder terms, are less than our threshold alpha value (0.05). This led us to presume that the aforementioned predictors are likely to be meaningful addition to our model.

Similar results were shown in shoulder and winter models where the first three lagged values of heat load predictors indicate meaningful significance. For workday and weekend models the heat load is most strongly correlated with present value of outdoor temperature (Temperature_lag0) compared to other time lags. One can notice that the workdays model in winter and shoulder term consists of lagged temperature value in the first previous hours (winter: Temperature_lag1 to Temperature_lag4, shoulder: Temperature_lag1).

The irradiation flux variable in workdays model of winter term is found to be absent, this mean there is no significance in explaining the response variable of heat load. Additionally, the models in winter and shoulder terms consists of lagged irradiation flux values in the first previous hours (winter/weekend: Irradiation.flux_lag0 to Irradiation.flux_lag2, shoulder/workdays: Irradiation.flux_lag1 to Irradiation.flux_lag6, shoulder/weekend: Irradiation.flux_lag4).

Furthermore (table 10 ,11) above list the regression coefficients and the significance level related to calendar data in winter and shoulder season. Most of the significant variables are spotted in early morning hours which could be explained by the increasing of heat load when the night scheduled setback periods end. The other significant variables could be attributed to the fact of using individual domestic heat water or manual temperature setting.

According to its coefficient, 8 am represent the peak demand compared to other hours of the days in winter and shoulder months. In general, this hour of the day is considered as the time of the daily morning system peak demand especially in winter term. In weekend models, on Saturday and Sunday at 10:00, a strong correlation with the heat load is spotted. This could be explained by the usual presence of private dwelling occupants in weekend morning.

4.1.2 Goodness of fit

Table 12. Model performance using different evaluation metrics

Evaluation Metrics	Winter Models		Shoulder Models	
	Workdays	Weekends	Workdays	Weekends
R-Squared	0.845	0.763	0.883	0.866
F-statistic	342.7	76.03	707	359.7
Prob (F-statistic)	8.52e-296	5.68e-80	0.00	1.17e-258

To evaluate the accuracy of the models table 12. above shows the different evaluation metrics that are used to characterize the heat load. In this perspective the shoulder season models yield an excellent fit to the observed data. For workdays models 88% of the variability observed in the target variables is explained by the regression model. In weekends the model explains 86 % of the variation in the response variable around its mean. The minimum value of R-squared is shown by the winter model, essentially for weekends model where 76 % of the variability observed in the heat load variable is explained by the regression model.

The F-value and probability (F-statistics) depict the overall significance of the regression model and the accuracy of the null hypothesis respectively. In this context, As illustrated in table 12 the F- value of all the models were exceedingly large numbers compared to the F-critical value. (In our case study the F-critical value was equal to 1 for a significance level of 0.05 ($\alpha=0.05$)). The models of the shoulder season displayed the higher F-statistic value particularly, in workdays model with a ratio of 707.

For the prob (F statistic) we could see that all the values were exceedingly small numbers. For that reason, the null hypothesis of the models was rejected.

4.1.3 Graphical Residual Analysis

Actual vs Predicted Data Graphs

The charts below (figure 33) show the representation of predicted values of the heat load against the actual values. These types of graphs are used to see the level of accuracy of our models.

A strong correlation can be seen between model prediction and its actual results for shoulder term (both workdays and weekends) (c, d) compared to winter models (a, b). The roughly horizontal profile refers to the domestic hot water consumption (DHW) which has less to no dependence against weather data.

In workdays and weekends models of the winter term, presented in sub figures (a, b), The model has two subsections of performance: In the first subsection, where the actual values are between 10 to 25 kWh, the model does not seem bad. In the second subsection, the model values are between 30 to 40 kWh. Within this zone the goodness of fit of the model is weak and the points are dispersed.

Figure 33. Predicted data vs Observed heat load: (a) winter (workday), (b) winter (weekend), (c) shoulder (workday), (d) shoulder (weekend)

We looked profoundly into the analysis of predicted and actual heat load graphs in monthly, weekly and daily scales for both winter and shoulder terms: In January and December as shown in fig 34. Below. The workday model shows a strong correlation with actual heat load values compared to same months in weekend model, where we see a randomness of the predicted heat load with the actual values.

Figure 34. Predicted data vs Observed heat load in January and December: (a) January (workday), (b) December (workday), (c) January (weekend), (d) December (weekend)

In weekly scale (winter term) the model performs poorly on Monday compared to other days. Fig 35 below demonstrates an example of heat load profile on Monday compared to Tuesday profile. We can observe a steady underestimation of the actual values essentially in the subsection where the heat load is greater than 20 kWh.

In contrast, at a daily basis we investigated the performance of the models in each hour of the day separately, we didn't see a noticeable difference between the hours of the day as shown in fig 36. Below. As a matter of fact, the predicted heat load values are close to the regressed diagonal line.

(a)

(b)

Figure 35. Predicted data vs Observed heat load on weekly basis (winter): (a) Monday, (b) Tuesday

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 36. Predicted data vs Observed heat load on daily basis (winter): (a) 04:00 (workdays), (b) 08:00 (workdays), (c) 22:00 (weekend)

In March and November (fig 37.) the workdays models showed a steady goodness of fit which is not the case in April and May. The two months show a weak relationship between predicted and actual heat load essentially within the zone of 0 to 5 kWh. The horizontal profile as explained in previous section indicate the non-dependency of domestic hot water consumption (DHW) to weather variables.

Figure 37. Predicted Data vs Observed heat load on monthly basis (shoulder months / workdays): (a) March, (b) November, (c) April, (d) May

Figure 38. Predicted data vs Observed heat load on monthly basis (shoulder months / weekends): (a) March, (b) November, (c) April, (d) May

Compared to workdays, the weekends of months in shoulder term, as presented in fig 38, showed a weak correlation between variables. In march, the models have clear two subsections of performance: In the first subsection, the model performs well, where the actual values are between 15 to 20 kWh. In the second subsection the model values are between 25 to 35 kWh where we see a randomness of the predicted heat load with the actual values.

As the heat load increases in the shoulder months, it become difficult to observe a steady estimation of the actual heat load which is illustrated in sub-figures (b, c, d).

Fig 39. Below shows the predicted against the observed heat load data. In this perspective, we can see that the early mornings of workdays and weekend models perform more accurately than the other hours of the days. The non-variability of the heat load in these times of hour could be explained by the night setback controlled by district heating operator.

Figure 39. Predicted data vs Observed heat load on daily basis (shoulder): (a) 03:00 (workdays), (b) 06:00 (workdays), (c) 22:00 (weekends), (d) 04:00 (weekend)

Residuals vs Predicted Data Graphs

Plotting residuals versus predicted value of heat load enables to detect non-linearity or unequal error variance in the models. In general, the response of heat load should produce a distribution of points scattered randomly around 0.

Fig 40. below displays the four models: (a) and (b) representing the workday and weekend models in winter period. (c) and (d) representing the workday and weekend models in shoulder period. The predicted heat load values are identified by the x-axis coupled with the standardized residuals identified by the y-axis. We called it standardized meaning each residual point at any plot are the same standardized Y-axis which help us to compare between the models.

In winter term models we can see clear inequality in error variance and the models have a tunnel shaped structure. Indeed, in the first subsection, in which the heat load value is between 0 to 25 kWh, the two models show a symmetrically distribution of residuals which is one of the assumptions to have ideal plot. However, in the second subsection (zone between 30 to 40 kWh) we observe a change in the variance, where the fitted values are dispersed from the middle line. This type of behavior is known as heteroscedasticity. It happens essentially when the spread of the fitted values against the residuals is non-constant.

The models in the shoulder terms (sub figures c, d) display a symmetrically distribution of predicted heat load values against the residuals. Within this distribution the values are clustered toward the middle of the plot, nevertheless we see a structural pattern particularly in the first

subsection within the zone of 0 to 10 kWh especially in the working model. This structural pattern suggest that the model has a room for improvement.

Figure 40. Predicted heat load data vs Standardized residuals: (a) workday model (winter), (b) weekend model (winter), (c) workday model (shoulder), (d) weekend model (shoulder)

Normal Q-Q Residual plots

The purpose of the residual normal Quantile-Quantile (Q-Q) plot is to assess the data skewness and judge the normality distribution of the residual points. Fig 38. below displays the normal residual Q-Q plot for the four models. The x-axis presents the theoretical quantile of the normal distribution The y-axis represents the sample quantile of the standardized residuals.

In winter term the models (sub figures a, b) show a clear similarity in the Q-Q plot shape. Approximately, from the values (-2.5,2) the sample seems to grow at the same pace as the standard normal distribution. Consequently, their quantiles match this region and the points are aligned along the line. From the values (2,3) the residual sample grows slower than the theoretical quantile, therefore it reaches its highest quantile before the standard normal

distribution. For this reason, we see a deviation from the line. This type of shape indicates that both two models have a room for improvement.

In shoulder season (sub figures c, d), approximately from the values (-3,2) the residuals sample grows slower than the standardized normal distribution, which it takes a longer time to increase. From (-2,1.5) The points are aligned along the line and the residual sample seems to grow at the same pace as the standard normal distribution. Lastly from the values (3,4) the sample grow faster than the standardized normal distribution, hence it reaches its highest quantile before the standard normal distribution. Typically, the S-shaped Q-Q plot indicate that the distribution has the correct median.

Figure 41. Normal Q-Q residual plots for winter and shoulder periods: (a) workday model (winter), (b) weekend model (winter), (c) workday model (shoulder), (d) weekend model (shoulder)

4.2. Data Scenarios and Model optimization to predict the heat load

The process of model optimization to predict the heat load was carried out by evaluating the effect of including various type of input parameters. In this context three different data scenarios have been created to each model in winter and shoulder season.

4.2.1 Models with Optimal Lagged Heat Load Variables

Table 13. Evaluation metrics with the inclusion depth lagged heat values (winter terms)

Winter term									
Lagged Heat Load variables	Workdays model				Lagged Heat Load variables	Weekends model			
	Adj R-squared	AIC	BIC	MAE		Adj R-squared	AIC	BIC	MAE
POWER1_lag1	0.728	3862	3871	2.092	POWER1_lag1	0.646	1490	1498	2.146
POWER1_lag2	0.782	3695	3709	1.911	POWER1_lag2	0.695	1447	1458	1.999
POWER1_lag3	0.797	3640	3658	1.837	POWER1_lag3	0.710	1432	1447	1.954
POWER1_lag4	0.797	3639	3663	1.838	POWER1_lag4	0.716	1427	1446	1.968
POWER1_lag5	0.799	3633	3661	1.823	POWER1_lag5	0.719	1425	1447	1.962
POWER1_lag6	0.799	3634	3666	1.822	POWER1_lag6	0.727	1417	1443	1.911
POWER1_lag7	0.800	3634	3671	1.827	POWER1_lag7	0.729	1416	1445	1.892
POWER1_lag8	0.801	3630	3672	1.822	POWER1_lag8	0.728	1418	1451	1.892
POWER1_lag9	0.800	3632	3679	1.822	POWER1_lag9	0.728	1419	1457	1.892
POWER1_lag10	0.801	3631	3682	1.814	POWER1_lag10	0.727	1421	1462	1.889
POWER1_lag11	0.804	3622	3678	1.802	POWER1_lag11	0.735	1413	1457	1.877
POWER1_lag12	0.804	3622	3682	1,800	POWER1_lag12	0.734	1415	1463	1.875

Table 13. presents the different evaluation metrics with the inclusion depth lagged heat values in winter terms. the models in both workdays and weekend start to perform significantly better after the inclusion of the second lagged heat load value. Generally, we can see that as soon we start to add the lagged predictors the overall metrics start to improve significantly, with an increase in the adjusted R-squared and a decrease in the Akaike information criterion (AIC), Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) and mean absolute errors (MAE).

In workdays model the increasing of the newly lagged heat load predictors to the 12th previous hours improve the adjusted R-squared with value of 0.804. Similar results are observed with the AIC where the model showed the best score with the inclusion of 11th hour of lagged heat load values. However, from the BIC metric we can see that the model could have a strong

relationship with the target variable when adding only three lagged values. Consequently, the workday model in winter term with added lagged heat load in the previous 3 hours is selected.

In weekend model the R-squared and the AIC of the model that include 11 lagged values has shown the preferred score. The optimal forecasting distance showed by the mean absolute error is seen at the inclusion of the 12th lagged values.

In contrast the BIC metric has showed a suitable option to select the model with lagged heat load variables, with only 6 lagged values.

Table 14. Evaluation metrics with the inclusion depth lagged heat values (shoulder season)

Lagged Heat Load variables	Workdays model				Lagged Heat Load variables	Weekends model			
	Adj R-squared	AIC	BIC	MAE		Adj R-squared	AIC	BIC	MAE
POWER1_lag1	0.837	7366	7382	1.947	POWER1_lag1	0.784	3000	3009	1.951
POWER1_lag2	0.837	7366	7382	1.824	POWER1_lag2	0.810	2921	2935	1.831
POWER1_lag3	0.838	7355	7377	1.812	POWER1_lag3	0.816	2902	2919	1.795
POWER1_lag4	0.838	7357	7384	1.812	POWER1_lag4	0.816	2904	2926	1.795
POWER1_lag5	0.838	7359	7391	1.811	POWER1_lag5	0.815	2907	2938	1.795
POWER1_lag6	0.838	7360	7398	1.810	POWER1_lag6	0.815	2907	2938	1.795
POWER1_lag7	0.838	7357	7400	1.812	POWER1_lag7	0.816	2905	2940	1.792
POWER1_lag8	0.838	7356	7404	1.815	POWER1_lag8	0.816	2906	2945	1.789
POWER1_lag9	0.838	7357	7411	1.816	POWER1_lag9	0.816	2907	2952	1.790
POWER1_lag10	0.838	7358	7417	1.817	POWER1_lag10	0.817	2907	2960	1.785
POWER1_lag11	0.839	7354	7418	1.815	POWER1_lag11	0.817	2907	2960	1.787
POWER1_lag12	0.840	7347	7417	1.813	POWER1_lag12	0.817	2907	2964	1.792

Table 14 (above) presents the different evaluation metrics with inclusion depth lagged heat load value in shoulder season. Interestingly, in workdays model the increase of the newly added lagged heat load did not significantly improve the adjusted R-squared.

Additionally, according to the AIC and BIC metrics the model did not improve after the inclusion of the second lagged heat load, contrarily to the mean absolute error (MAE) which decrease significantly over the past two hours of heat load. The best AIC and adjusted R-squared scores are captured at the 12th previous hours of lagged values. The MAE has reached its maximum decrease at the 6th lagged heat load value.

The selection of the optimal lagged value in workdays model was based on the BIC evaluation metric which present the best score when adding 3 lagged predictors.

In weekend model, the overall evaluation metrics have increased significantly as soon as we start adding the second lagged value. The best score of the MAE is showed when adding 12 lagged variables. These predictors were reduced to 3 lagged values depending on the three-evaluation metrics: adjusted R-squared, AIC and BIC.

In general, the results show that the weekend model along with the workdays model depend on the heat load of previous three hours in term of model prediction accuracy.

Table 15. Equations of the models that include optimal lagged heat load inputs (1st data scenario)

	Winter term		Shoulder season	
Data scenarios	Workday model	Weekend model	Workday model	Weekend model
Lagged Heat Load Inputs variables	$Q = C_0 + C_{Q1} \times Q_1 + C_{Q2} \times Q_2 + C_{Q3} \times Q_3 + w_i$	$Q = C_0 + C_{Q1} \times Q_1 + C_{Q2} \times Q_2 + C_{Q3} \times Q_3 \dots + C_{Q6} \times Q_6 + w_i$	$Q = C_0 + C_{Q1} \times Q_1 + C_{Q2} \times Q_2 + C_{Q3} \times Q_3 + w_i$	$Q = C_0 + C_{Q1} \times Q_1 + C_{Q2} \times Q_2 + C_{Q3} \times Q_3 + w_i$

Table 15. provides the equations of the models that include optimal lagged heat load inputs. In order to determine the optimal number of coefficients, three lagged values were taken for the heat load of the building in shoulder models and workdays model of the winter terms except for the weekend model where 6 lagged heat load inputs were taken.

4.2.2 Models with Optimal Lagged Weather Variables

Temperature Lagged Variables

Table 16. below presents the different evaluation metrics with the inclusion depth lagged temperature values in winter terms. At first glance, we can see that using only present information (temperature_lag0) for both workdays and weekends can greatly improve the models. However, this configuration is potentially too exposed to the impact of weather forecasting.

In workdays model as soon we start to add the lagged temperature predictors, the adjusted R-squared and the mean absolute error (MAE) start to improve significantly showing the best score at 12th previous hours with a value of 0.832. Similar results have been detected when evaluating the Akaike information criterion (AIC), where the increasing of the newly lagged temperature values to the 12th previous hours shows a better model in term of prediction

accuracy. Compared to the aforementioned evaluation metrics (Adj R-squared, AIC and MAE), the Bayesian information criterion (BIC) shows a great improvement in the performance of the model only with lagged value of temperature.

In weekend model, after the inclusion of coefficient of lagged temperature predictors to 5 lagged values, we did not see an improvement in the performance of models according to adjusted R-squared and AIC evaluation metrics. The mean absolute error decrease slightly with every addition of lagged value. The best score is recorded at the inclusion of 19th hour of temperature lagged values (1.764), However the BIC has recorded its maximum decrease only at the first lagged signal

From both two models we can see that the best optimal lagged values are selected based on the Bayesian information criterion (BIC) as highlighted in the table.

Table 16. Evaluation metrics with the inclusion depth lagged temperature values (winter term)

Winter term									
Lagged Temperature Variables	Workdays model				Lagged Temperature Variables	Weekends model			
	Adj R-squared	AIC	BIC	MAE		Adj R-squared	AIC	BIC	MAE
Temperature_lag0	0.824	3530	3554	1.757	Temperature_lag0	0.748	1394	1423	1.844
Temperature_lag1	0.824	3531	3559	1.757	Temperature_lag1	0.750	1393	1427	1.829
Temperature_lag2	0.824	3533	3565	1.756	Temperature_lag2	0.749	1395	1432	1.825
Temperature_lag3	0.824	3534	3571	1.757	Temperature_lag3	0.749	1396	1437	1.822
Temperature_lag4	0.824	3535	3577	1.760	Temperature_lag4	0.748	1398	1442	1.823
Temperature_lag5	0.825	3531	3577	1.757	Temperature_lag5	0.754	1392	1440	1.795
Temperature_lag6	0.825	3531	3582	1.757	Temperature_lag6	0.754	1393	1445	1.802
Temperature_lag7	0.825	3532	3588	1.754	Temperature_lag7	0.754	1394	1449	1.799
Temperature_lag8	0.829	3514	3575	1.742	Temperature_lag8	0.753	1396	1455	1.799
Temperature_lag9	0.829	3516	3581	1.742	Temperature_lag9	0.754	1396	1459	1.799
Temperature_lag10	0.830	3513	3583	1.745	Temperature_lag10	0.754	1397	1464	1.789
Temperature_lag11	0.831	3511	3585	1.742	Temperature_lag11	0.753	1399	1469	1.789
Temperature_lag12	0.832	3509	3588	1.743	Temperature_lag12	0.752	1400	1474	1.785
Temperature_lag13	0.832	3510	3594	1.738	Temperature_lag13	0.752	1402	1480	1.790
Temperature_lag14	0.832	3510	3598	1.738	Temperature_lag14	0.751	1404	1485	1.789
Temperature_lag15	0.832	3512	3604	1.736	Temperature_lag15	0.750	1406	1491	1.790
Temperature_lag16	0.832	3511	3609	1.736	Temperature_lag16	0.751	1405	1494	1.776
Temperature_lag17	0.832	3512	3614	1.735	Temperature_lag17	0.751	1407	1499	1.778
Temperature_lag18	0.832	3513	3619	1.732	Temperature_lag18	0.753	1405	1501	1.765
Temperature_lag19	0.832	3514	3626	1.732	Temperature_lag19	0.752	1407	1507	1.764
Temperature_lag20	0.832	3514	3631	1.729	Temperature_lag20	0.753	1407	1511	1.768

Temperature_lag21	0.832	3516	3637	1.729	Temperature_lag21	0.752	1409	1516	1.766
Temperature_lag22	0.832	3517	3642	1.726	Temperature_lag22	0.752	1410	1521	1.767
Temperature_lag23	0.832	3519	3649	1.724	Temperature_lag23	0.752	1410	1525	1.765
Temperature_lag24	0.832	3521	3655	1.724	Temperature_lag24	0.752	1412	1531	1.767

Table 17. Evaluation metrics with the inclusion depth lagged temperature values (shoulder season)

Shoulder term									
Lagged Temperature Variables	Workdays model				Lagged Temperature Variables	Weekends model			
	Adj R-squared	AIC	BIC	MAE		Adj R-squared	AIC	BIC	MAE
Temperature_lag0	0.869	7020	7047	1.682	Temperature_lag0	0.851	2769	2791	1.638
Temperature_lag1	0.875	6946	6978	1.650	Temperature_lag1	0.855	2754	2781	1.633
Temperature_lag2	0.877	6929	6966	1.648	Temperature_lag2	0.857	2747	2778	1.627
Temperature_lag3	0.877	6931	6974	1.648	Temperature_lag3	0.857	2749	2785	1.626
Temperature_lag4	0.877	6930	6978	1.643	Temperature_lag4	0.857	2751	2791	1.625
Temperature_lag5	0.877	6928	6981	1.638	Temperature_lag5	0.856	2753	2797	1.624
Temperature_lag6	0.877	6924	6983	1.635	Temperature_lag6	0.857	2751	2800	1.618
Temperature_lag7	0.877	6926	6990	1.635	Temperature_lag7	0.857	2750	2803	1.614
Temperature_lag8	0.877	6927	6997	1.634	Temperature_lag8	0.858	2749	2807	1.614
Temperature_lag9	0.877	6929	7004	1.633	Temperature_lag9	0.858	2749	2811	1.615
Temperature_lag10	0.877	6928	7008	1.630	Temperature_lag10	0.858	2749	2816	1.614
Temperature_lag11	0.877	6929	7015	1.630	Temperature_lag11	0.858	2751	2822	1.613
Temperature_lag12	0.877	6931	7027	1.628	Temperature_lag12	0.858	2753	2828	1.613
Temperature_lag13	0.877	6931	7027	1.626	Temperature_lag13	0.859	2750	2830	1.600
Temperature_lag14	0.877	6935	7042	1.626	Temperature_lag14	0.859	2751	2835	1.600
Temperature_lag15	0.877	6935	7042	1.626	Temperature_lag15	0.859	2752	2841	1.598
Temperature_lag16	0.877	6936	7048	1.627	Temperature_lag16	0.859	2753	2846	1.597
Temperature_lag17	0.877	6938	7056	1.627	Temperature_lag17	0.858	2755	2853	1.597
Temperature_lag18	0.877	6938	7061	1.627	Temperature_lag18	0.858	2757	2859	1.597
Temperature_lag19	0.877	6940	7068	1.627	Temperature_lag19	0.858	2759	2865	1.596
Temperature_lag20	0.878	6932	7066	1.619	Temperature_lag20	0.858	2761	2872	1.597
Temperature_lag21	0.878	6931	7070	1.620	Temperature_lag21	0.858	2762	2877	1.591
Temperature_lag22	0.878	6933	7078	1.620	Temperature_lag22	0.858	2763	2882	1.590
Temperature_lag23	0.878	6934	7084	1.619	Temperature_lag23	0.858	2763	2887	1.590
Temperature_lag24	0.878	6935	7090	1.618	Temperature_lag24	0.858	2765	2893	1.589

Table 17. presents the different evaluation metrics with the inclusion depth lagged temperature in shoulder season. The mean absolute error (MAE) decreases slightly in both workday and

weekend model with every addition of lagged temperature value. the best MAE score was recorded at the 24th previous hour lagged temperature.

In Workday model the best value of adjusted R-squared was recorded at the 20th previous hour. The model starts to perform significantly better after the inclusion of the second lagged temperature value in which we have seen a significant decrease in the AIC metric. This decrease reaches its maximum at the 6th previous hour of lagged temperature value. The best optimal model in term of lagged temperature variables was chosen based on the Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) with a selection of two optimal lagged values.

In weekend the inclusion of lagged temperature, up to 13 values, showed a slightly improvement in the performance of the model, However the best optimal number of lagged signals were selected based on the AIC and BIC evaluation metrics with only 2 lagged values.

Irradiation flux Lagged Variables

Table 18. Evaluation metrics with the inclusion depth lagged irradiation flux values (winter)

Winter term									
Lagged Irradiation Flux variables	Workdays model				Lagged Irradiation Flux variables	Weekends model			
	Adj R-squared	AIC	BIC	MAE		Adj R-squared	AIC	BIC	MAE
Irradiation.flux_lag0	0.826	3522	3555	1.755	Irradiation.flux_lag0	0.749	1395	1432	1.821
Irradiation.flux_lag1	0.826	3524	3561	1.756	Irradiation.flux_lag1	0.750	1395	1436	1.819
Irradiation.flux_lag2	0.826	3525	3567	1.755	Irradiation.flux_lag2	0.750	1396	1440	1.819
Irradiation.flux_lag3	0.826	3527	3573	1.753	Irradiation.flux_lag3	0.751	1396	1444	1.812
Irradiation.flux_lag4	0.826	3528	3579	1.751	Irradiation.flux_lag4	0.750	1398	1449	1.812
Irradiation.flux_lag5	0.827	3524	3580	1.754	Irradiation.flux_lag5	0.750	1399	1454	1.809
Irradiation.flux_lag6	0.827	3525	3586	1.755	Irradiation.flux_lag6	0.750	1400	1459	1.806
Irradiation.flux_lag7	0.828	3520	3585	1.751	Irradiation.flux_lag7	0.749	1402	1465	1.807
Irradiation.flux_lag8	0.828	3522	3592	1.751	Irradiation.flux_lag8	0.748	1404	1470	1.806
Irradiation.flux_lag9	0.829	3521	3596	1.748	Irradiation.flux_lag9	0.747	1405	1476	1.799
Irradiation.flux_lag10	0.828	3523	3602	1.749	Irradiation.flux_lag10	0.749	1404	1478	1.781
Irradiation.flux_lag11	0.829	3523	3607	1.742	Irradiation.flux_lag11	0.749	1406	1484	1.780
Irradiation.flux_lag12	0.829	3524	3612	1.741	Irradiation.flux_lag12	0.750	1405	1486	1.790
Irradiation.flux_lag13	0.828	3526	3619	1.741	Irradiation.flux_lag13	0.753	1402	1488	1.796
Irradiation.flux_lag14	0.829	3524	3622	1.739	Irradiation.flux_lag14	0.753	1404	1493	1.793
Irradiation.flux_lag15	0.829	3525	3627	1.741	Irradiation.flux_lag15	0.752	1405	1498	1.792
Irradiation.flux_lag16	0.829	3527	3633	1.741	Irradiation.flux_lag16	0.752	1407	1503	1.787
Irradiation.flux_lag17	0.829	3528	3639	1.737	Irradiation.flux_lag17	0.751	1408	1508	1.788
Irradiation.flux_lag18	0.829	3529	3645	1.736	Irradiation.flux_lag18	0.752	1408	1512	1.783

Irradiation.flux_lag19	0.829	3531	3652	1.736	Irradiation.flux_lag19	0.752	1409	1517	1.780
Irradiation.flux_lag20	0.828	3533	3658	1.736	Irradiation.flux_lag20	0.752	1410	1521	1.774
Irradiation.flux_lag21	0.828	3535	3665	1.736	Irradiation.flux_lag21	0.751	1412	1526	1.773
Irradiation.flux_lag22	0.828	3537	3671	1.737	Irradiation.flux_lag22	0.751	1413	1532	1.769
Irradiation.flux_lag23	0.829	3535	3674	1.732	Irradiation.flux_lag23	0.750	1415	1537	1.770
Irradiation.flux_lag24	0.829	3536	3680	1.729	Irradiation.flux_lag24	0.753	1412	1538	1.751

Table 18. above presents the different evaluation metrics with inclusion depth lagged irradiation flux in winter term. In both workday and weekend, the preferred result of MAE was recorded at 24th previous hour of lagged predictors (Irradiation_flux_lag24).

In workday model the increasing of the newly lagged heat load predictors to the 9th previous hour improves the adjusted R-squared with value 0.829. Similar results are observed with the AIC where the model showed the best score with the inclusion of the 7th hour of lagged irradiation flux values. However, from the BIC metric we can see that the model has strong relationship with the target variables when adding only one lagged value.

In weekend model the R-squared and the AIC of the model that include 11 lagged values has shown the preferred score. Consequently, the workday and weekend models in winter terms with one lagged value have been selected.

Table 19 below presents the different evaluation metrics with inclusion depth lagged irradiation flux in shoulder term. In both workdays and weekends the preferred result of the adjusted R-squared was recorded at 11th previous hour of lagged predictors.

In workday model as soon, we start to add the lagged irradiation flux predictors, the AIC start to improve significantly showing the best score at the 17th previous hour with a value of 6900. Similar results have been detected when evaluating the mean absolute error (MAE) where the increasing of the newly lagged irradiation flux values to the 19th previous hours have shown a better model in term of prediction accuracy. Compared to the aforementioned evaluation metrics (AIC and MAE) the Bayesian information criterion (BIC) has shown a great improvement in the performance of the model only with two lagged values.

In weekend model after the inclusion of coefficient of lagged irradiation flux predictors to 11 lagged values, we did not see an improvement in the performance of models according to AIC evaluation metric. The mean absolute error decrease slightly with every addition of lagged value. The best score is recorded with the inclusion of 24th hour of irradiation flux.

Table 19. Evaluation metrics with the inclusion depth lagged irradiation flux values (shoulder season)

Shoulder term									
Lagged Irradiation Flux variables	Workdays model				Lagged Irradiation Flux variables	Weekends model			
	Adj R-squared	AIC	BIC	MAE		Adj R-squared	AIC	BIC	MAE
Irradiation.flux_lag0	0.877	6926	6969	1.672	Irradiation.flux_lag0	0.857	2748	2783	1.627
Irradiation.flux_lag1	0.877	6922	6971	1.660	Irradiation.flux_lag1	0.857	2749	2789	1.625
Irradiation.flux_lag2	0.878	6909	6963	1.645	Irradiation.flux_lag2	0.858	2746	2791	1.623
Irradiation.flux_lag3	0.879	6904	6963	1.641	Irradiation.flux_lag3	0.858	2748	2797	1.623
Irradiation.flux_lag4	0.879	6904	6968	1.638	Irradiation.flux_lag4	0.858	2746	2799	1.615
Irradiation.flux_lag5	0.879	6904	6974	1.637	Irradiation.flux_lag5	0.858	2748	2805	1.614
Irradiation.flux_lag6	0.879	6902	6977	1.635	Irradiation.flux_lag6	0.859	2746	2808	1.615
Irradiation.flux_lag7	0.879	6903	6983	1.631	Irradiation.flux_lag7	0.858	2748	2815	1.614
Irradiation.flux_lag8	0.879	6903	6989	1.632	Irradiation.flux_lag8	0.859	2747	2818	1.608
Irradiation.flux_lag9	0.879	6905	6996	1.631	Irradiation.flux_lag9	0.859	2749	2824	1.608
Irradiation.flux_lag10	0.879	6903	7000	1.631	Irradiation.flux_lag10	0.859	2747	2827	1.601
Irradiation.flux_lag11	0.880	6901	7003	1.630	Irradiation.flux_lag11	0.861	2742	2827	1.597
Irradiation.flux_lag12	0.880	6902	7009	1.630	Irradiation.flux_lag12	0.860	2744	2833	1.597
Irradiation.flux_lag13	0.880	6901	7014	1.628	Irradiation.flux_lag13	0.860	2746	2839	1.596
Irradiation.flux_lag14	0.880	6902	7020	1.629	Irradiation.flux_lag14	0.860	2747	2845	1.594
Irradiation.flux_lag15	0.880	6904	7027	1.628	Irradiation.flux_lag15	0.860	2747	2849	1.592
Irradiation.flux_lag16	0.880	6905	7033	1.628	Irradiation.flux_lag16	0.860	2748	2855	1.591
Irradiation.flux_lag17	0.880	6900	7034	1.623	Irradiation.flux_lag17	0.860	2750	2861	1.591
Irradiation.flux_lag18	0.880	6902	7042	1.623	Irradiation.flux_lag18	0.861	2749	2865	1.590
Irradiation.flux_lag19	0.880	6903	7047	1.620	Irradiation.flux_lag19	0.860	2751	2871	1.590
Irradiation.flux_lag20	0.880	6904	7054	1.621	Irradiation.flux_lag20	0.860	2753	2878	1.590
Irradiation.flux_lag21	0.880	6906	7061	1.621	Irradiation.flux_lag21	0.860	2754	2882	1.586
Irradiation.flux_lag22	0.880	6903	7064	1.621	Irradiation.flux_lag22	0.860	2756	2889	1.586
Irradiation.flux_lag23	0.880	6905	7071	1.621	Irradiation.flux_lag23	0.860	2755	2892	1.580
Irradiation.flux_lag24	0.880	6907	7078	1.621	Irradiation.flux_lag24	0.860	2756	2898	1.579

Selection of The Best Subset of Lagged Temperature and Irradiation Flux Variables

Figure 42. Evaluation of different subsets of models in winter terms: (a) workday model, (b) weekend model

The evaluation of different subsets of models in winter for both workdays and weekends was illustrated in fig 42 above. The Bayesian information criterion is chosen as the evaluation metrics to be used due to its capability to measure the parameterized models in term of predicting data.

In sub-figure (a), the three models share the same number of lagged values in term of temperature and irradiation flux with up to 1-hour historical data. Furthermore, the increase of number of lagged heat load (Q) has resulted in a decrease in the BIC value. The lowest BIC score was represented by the Q3_T1_I1. Thus, this model was selected for the workdays model in winter term.

The evaluation of different subsets of models in weekends in term of BIC metric is shown in sub-figure (b). As can be seen after adding up to 3 hours historical heat load data, the performance of the models started to drop which was explained the increase of the BIC metrics. The BIC of the Q1_T1_I1 model is lower than Q2_T1_I1 and Q3_T1_I1 which are equivalent. Thus, we have selected this model (Q_T1_I1) since it is simpler than the two other models and incorporate less variables.

The evaluation of different subsets of models in shoulder term for both workdays and weekends was illustrated in fig 43 and fig 44 below. In fig 43 the models that have one lagged in heat load values has resulted an important decline in the Bayesian information criterion metric up to 6980. The Q3_T2_I2 model was selected since it represents the lowest value of BIC (6963).

The evaluation of different subsets of models in weekends in term of BIC metrics is shown in fig 44. Compared to other models, Q1_T1_I1 and Q1_T2_I1 perform poorly with regard to prediction accuracy. We can see that adding newly lagged heat load predictors improve the performance of the models. Q3_T1_I1 and Q3_T2_I1 showed the best score, however, we chose only Q3_T1_I1 since it has the smaller number of variables.

Figure 43. Evaluation of different subsets of models in shoulder season (workday)

Figure 44. Evaluation of different subsets of models in shoulder season (weekend)

Table 20. Equations of the models that include optimal lagged weather inputs (2nd data scenario)

	Winter term		Shoulder season	
Data scenarios	Workday model	Weekend model	Workday model	Weekend model
Lagged Weather Input variables (Temperature and Irradiation flux)	$Q = C_0 + C_{Q1} \times Q_1 + C_{Q2} \times Q_2 + C_{Q3} \times Q_3 + C_{T0} \times T_0 + C_{T1} \times T_1 + C_{I0} \times I_0 + C_{I1} \times I_1 + w_i$	$Q = C_0 + C_{Q1} \times Q_1 + C_{T0} \times T_0 + C_{T1} \times T_1 + C_{I0} \times I_0 + C_{I1} \times I_1 + w_i$	$Q = C_0 + C_{Q1} \times Q_1 + C_{Q2} \times Q_2 + C_{Q3} \times Q_3 + C_{T0} \times T_0 + C_{T1} \times T_1 + C_{T2} \times T_2 + C_{I0} \times I_0 + C_{I1} \times I_1 + C_{I2} \times I_2 + w_i$	$Q = C_0 + C_{Q1} \times Q_1 + C_{Q2} \times Q_2 + C_{Q3} \times Q_3 + C_{T0} \times T_0 + C_{T1} \times T_1 + C_{I0} \times I_0 + C_{I1} \times I_1 + w_i$

Table 20. displays the equations of the models that include optimal lagged weather variable inputs. The models were selected based on their performance of prediction accuracy using Bayesian information criterion (BIC).

In winter term Q3_T1_I1 and Q1_T1_I1 were selected for workdays and weekends respectively as the models having the optimal lagged explanatory variables. In shoulder season models with 3 previous hours lagged heat load and 2 lagged values of temperature and irradiation flux were taken for workdays (Q3_T2_I2). Regarding the weekend model three lagged value of heat load including one lagged value of temperature and irradiation flux were added. (Q3_T1_I1).

4.2.3 Models with Significant Calendar Data Variables

Table 21 and table 22 below show the evaluation metrics of all possible subsets of significant calendar data variables. Three evaluation metrics (Adjusted R-squared, AIC and BIC) were selected to assess the quality of models in term of prediction.

In workdays (table21), when including all the significant hours of the week, the adjusted R-squared reached its maximum at 0.833 where 83.3 % of all variation in the heat load response variable explained around its mean. Nevertheless, dropping out the hours of 16:00 on Friday has increased the performance of the model in which the AIC has showed the best score (AIC=3479). The lowest value of BIC was shown after excluding the Friday's hours at 05:00 and 16:00. Therefore, the Bayesian Information Criterion was the best metric to depend on in selecting the workdays model.

In winter term weekends (table22) the performance of the model was satisfactory when including all the significant calendar data variables. According to the adjusted R-squared, the model can explain 71.6% of all variation in the heat load response variables around its mean.

Moreover, the load showed the lowest values of Akaike Information Criterion (AIC= 1455) and a value of 1496 regarding the Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC).

Table 21. Evaluation metrics with the significant calendar data variables (winter terms / workdays)

Winter term / workdays								
Variables to enter						Evaluation metrics		
Tuesday1h	Wednesday 3h	Wednesday 7h	Friday 5h	Friday 16h	Monday 8h	Adj R- squared	AIC	BIC
×						0.829	3493	3535
×	×					0.830	3490	3537
×	×	×				0.831	3488	3539
×	×	×	×			0.832	3485	3541
×	×	×	×	×		0.833	3482	3542
×	×	×	×	×	×	0.833	3482	3542
	×					0.829	3494	3536
		×				0.829	3494	3536
		×	×			0.830	3490	3537
			×			0.829	3495	3537
×			×			0.830	3491	3537
×	×		×			0.831	3488	3539
				×		0.829	3493	3535
×				×		0.830	3489	3536
×	×			×		0.831	3487	3538
×	×	×		×		0.832	3484	3540
					×	0.830	3491	3528
×					×	0.831	3487	3528
×	×				×	0.832	3484	3530
×	×	×			×	0.833	3481	3532
×	×	×	×		×	0.833	3479	3535

Table 22. Evaluation metrics with significant calendar data variables (winter term / weekends)

Winter term / weekend							
Variables to enter					Evaluation metrics		
Saturday 2h	Saturday 10h	Sunday 1h	Sunday 4h	Sunday 5h	Adj R-squared	AIC	BIC
x					0.690	1479	1505
x	x				0.701	1469	1499
x	x	x			0.705	1465	1499
x	x	x	x		0.711	1459	1496
x	x	x	x	x	0.716	1455	1496
	x				0.696	1472	1498
		x			0.690	1479	1505
x		x			0.694	1475	1505
			x		0.692	1477	1503
x			x		0.697	1473	1503
x	x		x		0.707	1463	1497
				x	0.689	1479	1505
x				x	0.694	1476	1506
x	x			x	0.704	1466	1500
x	x	x		x	0.708	1462	1500

Table 23 and 24 below, show the evaluation metrics of all possible subsets of significant calendar data variables in shoulder months. In workdays (table 23) including only Friday's hours at 10:00 as predictor improved the model with a best value of BIC (BIC = 7153). However, other hours of the workdays were helpful in improving the model. In our case we clearly have seen the increasing of the performance of the model (including the hours of Thursday at 02:00, the early morning Friday's hours (Friday 07:00, Friday 10:00 and Friday 11:00, the evening Friday's hours and Monday's hours at 01:00 and 08:00). Using these variables has given the lowest value of AIC evaluation metrics (AIC= 7070).

Despite having the best BIC value (BIC = 2781) in weekends model (table 24), including only one predictor variable (Sunday 18:00) was not sufficient to reach the maximum score of adjusted R-squared. That's why including all significant variables has improved the model performance. The adjusted R-squared was increased to reach a value 0.861, meaning 86.1% of all variation in the heat load response variable was explained around its mean.

Table 23. Evaluation metrics with significant calendar data variables (shoulder / workdays)

Shoulder months / workdays										
Variables to enter								Evaluation metrics		
Thursday 2h	Friday 7h	Friday 10h	Friday 11h	Friday 21h	Monday 0h	Monday 1h	Monday 8h	Adj R- squared	AIC	BIC
x								0.880	7099	7158
x	x							0.880	7097	7161
x	x	x						0.881	7089	7159
x	x	x	x					0.881	7086	7161
x	x	x	x	x				0.881	7083	7164
x	x	x	x	x	x			0.882	7079	7165
x	x	x	x	x	x	x		0.882	7076	7168
x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	0.882	7070	7167
	x							0.880	7099	7159
		x						0.880	7094	7153
x		x						0.880	7091	7156
			x					0.880	7098	7158
x			x					0.880	7096	7160
x	x		x					0.880	7094	7164
				x				0.880	7099	7158
x				x				0.880	7096	7161
x	x			x				0.880	7094	7164
x	x	x		x				0.881	7087	7162
					x			0.880	7098	7157
x					x			0.880	7095	7159
x	x				x			0.880	7093	7163
x	x	x			x			0.881	7085	7160
x	x	x	x		x			0.881	7082	7162
						x		0.880	7099	7158
x						x		0.880	7096	7160
x	x					x		0.880	7094	7164
x	x	x				x		0.881	7086	7161
x	x	x	x			x		0.881	7083	7163
x	x	x	x	x		x		0.881	7080	7166
							x	0.880	7095	7154
x							x	0.880	7093	7157
x	x						x	0.881	7090	7160
x	x	x					x	0.881	7083	7158
x	x	x	x				x	0.881	7080	7160
x	x	x	x	x			x	0.882	7077	7163

x	x	x	x	x	x		x	0.882	7073	7165
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Table 24. Evaluation metrics with significant calendar data variables (shoulder / weekends)

Shoulder months / Weekends								
Variables to enter						Evaluation metrics		
Saturday 22h	Sunday 15h	Sunday 16h	Sunday 18h	Sunday 19h	Sunday 22h	Adj R- squared	AIC	BIC
x						0.857	2744	2784
x	x					0.858	2743	2787
x	x	x				0.858	2742	2791
x	x	x	x			0.860	2736	2790
x	x	x	x	x		0.861	2732	2790
x	x	x	x	x	x	0.861	2730	2792
	x					0.857	2745	2784
		x				0.857	2745	2785
x		x				0.858	2743	2788
			x			0.858	2741	2781
x			x			0.859	2739	2784
x	x		x			0.859	2738	2787
				x		0.857	2743	2783
x				x		0.858	2741	2785
x	x			x		0.859	2740	2788
x	x	x		x		0.859	2738	2792
					x	0.857	2745	2785
x					x	0.858	2743	2787
x	x				x	0.858	2742	2791
x	x	x			x	0.859	2741	2794
x	x	x	x		x	0.860	2735	2793

Table 25. Equations of the models that include significant calendar data inputs (3rd data scenario)

Data scenarios	Winter term		Shoulder season	
	Workday model	Weekend model	Workday model	Weekend model
Significant Calendar Data variables (Hours of the week)	$Q = C_0 + C_{Q1} \times Q_1 + C_{Q2} \times Q_2 + C_{Q3} \times Q_3 + C_{T0} \times T_0 + C_{T1} \times T_1 + C_{I0} \times I_0 + C_{I1} \times I_1 + w_i + TUE_{1h} + WED_{3h} + WED_{7h} + MON_{8h}$	$Q = C_0 + C_{Q1} \times Q_1 + C_{T0} \times T_0 + C_{T1} \times T_1 + C_{I0} \times I_0 + C_{I1} \times I_1 + w_i + SAT_{2h} + SAT_{10h} + SUN_{1h} + SUN_{4h} + SUN_{5h}$	$Q = C_0 + C_{Q1} \times Q_1 + C_{Q2} \times Q_2 + C_{Q3} \times Q_3 + C_{T0} \times T_0 + C_{T1} \times T_1 + C_{T2} \times T_2 + C_{I0} \times I_0 + C_{I1} \times I_1 + C_{I2} \times I_2 + w_i + THU_{2h} + FRI_{7h} + FRI_{10h} + FRI_{11h} + FRI_{21h} + MON_{0h} + MON_{1h} + MON_{8h}$	$Q = C_0 + C_{Q1} \times Q_1 + C_{Q2} \times Q_2 + C_{Q3} \times Q_3 + C_{T0} \times T_0 + C_{T1} \times T_1 + C_{I0} \times I_0 + C_{I1} \times I_1 + w_i + SAT_{22h} + SUN_{15h} + SUN_{16h} + SUN_{18h} + SUN_{19h} + SUN_{22h}$

Table 25 represents the models of the 3rd data scenario which include significant calendar data inputs.

The workdays model in winter term is denoted by **Q3_T1_I1** (TUE_1h_WED_3,7h_MON_8h) : Q3 represents the heat load with three lagged values, T1, I1 represent the lagged values at 1-hour historical data for temperature and irradiation flux respectively. WED_3,7h refers to the significant predictors of hours at 03:00 and 7:00 on Wednesday, MON_8h refers to the significant predictors of hours 08:00 on Monday.

The same notation was used for the other models. The weekends model in winter term is denoted by **Q1_T1_I1** (SAT_2,10h_SUN_1,4,5h). The workdays model in shoulder season is denoted by **Q3_T2_I2** (THU_2h_FRI_7,10,11,21h_MON_0,1,8h). The weekends model in shoulder season is denoted by **Q3_T1_I1** (SAT_22h_SUN_15,16,18,19,22h).

4.3. Model Selection and Testing

The model selection and testing process has been performed in two main steps: First, among the various types of input data, the best data scenario that generate more accurate prediction was selected for each model as input parameters. Second, the selected models have been tested. Essentially, the seasonal performance variation of the heat load throughout the year were evaluated for each model.

4.3.1 Comparison of Models' performance with Different Data Scenarios

Scenarios

Figure 45. Root mean square error of the four forecast models (workdays-winter, weekend-winter, workdays-shoulder and weekend-shoulder) for each data scenario

Figure 46. Mean absolute error of the four forecast models (workdays-winter, weekends-winter, workdays-shoulder and weekends-shoulder) for each data scenario

From figure 45 and figure 46 above, we observe some variation between the magnitude of the mean absolute error (MAE) and the root mean square errors (RMSE). As a matter of fact, the RMSE is more sensitive to outliers and penalizes the larger error that's why the value of root mean square errors are higher than the mean absolute errors.

Models with only lagged heat load variables stands out by performing significantly worse than models with other data scenarios (lagged weather variables and significant calendar data). In this perspective, winter models have the highest values of RMSE and MAE compared to shoulder models in all the three data scenarios. (Particularly the weekend model in winter terms with an RMSE value of 3.254 kWh and an MAE value of 2.334 kWh).

Adding lagged weather variables of temperature and irradiation flux drastically increase the performance of all the four models which is explained by the decreasing value of the mean absolute error (MAE) and the root mean square error (RMSE).

One can see in both figures that adding the significant calendar data slightly improve the performance of the models. The focus in the rest of this work will be on the four models of the 3rd data scenario using significant calendar data.

4.3.2 Seasonal Performance Variation

(A)

(B)

(C)

Figure 47. Performance of the four models in each month, where the forecast error varies with time of the days, using the significant calendar data: (A) winter / workdays model, (B) winter / weekend model, (C) shoulder /workdays model, (D) shoulder /weekend model

As shown in figure 47. Above the heat load varies over the year in magnitude and variation. Three different evaluation metrics are shown: on the left axis the mean absolute percentage error (MAPE), on the right axis the mean absolute error (MAE) and root mean square error (RMSE). The hours of the day are represented by the horizontal axis.

We can see that the RMSE and MAE appear to be large in winter term compared to shoulder months. In this context the evaluation metrics are large in the evening hours, this could be explained by the large heat load with large variance during the winter months. The RMSE and MAE can be above 4 kWh and 3 kWh in some hours especially in January whereas in shoulder term it can be below 2 kWh especially in April.

The MAPE behaves in opposite way compared to RMSE and MAE metrics, generally the aforementioned metric is smaller in winter months with a value between 4 to 20 % and larger in shoulder months with values between 20 to 80 %. These large values of MAPE indicate the inaccuracy of forecasting in some hours of shoulder months especially for April, May and September where we observe a peak of MAPE particularly between 10:00 to 15:00.

As a whole we didn't spot any clear pattern of error change during the day. Moreover, the performance of the four models doesn't seem to be bad in early morning particularly between 3:00 to 4:00.

The aggregated error metrics such as RMSE, MAE and MAPE do not tell us the full story regarding the forecast variation over the year. As a matter of fact, identifying maximum error can be helpful in the heat load production planning and also can ensure the evaluation risk to cover the heating load day by day.

Figure 48 below represents histogram for the hourly errors for each month. The 10% and 90% quantiles are specified. In this context the width of the error's distribution varies from month to month.

In the shoulder season the forecast errors are more or less confined particularly in October of weekend model. While in the winter term the distribution errors widen specifically in January month of the weekend model. In addition, the distribution of errors is not completely symmetric around 0. In March (workday model), for example, the distribution is shifted to the positive side. However, in May (weekend model) the distribution is shifted to the negative side.

In table 26. below a summary of the error distribution is represented. The 99% and 1% quantiles indicate the maximum errors. In winter term the best month of workdays model is December with 98% falling between -4.07 kWh and 4.69 kWh, while January is the worst month where 99% of errors are below 9.70 kWh and 1% of data are less or equal -5.78 kWh.

The best month of weekend model is February with 98% of the errors falling between -2.60 kWh and 4.42 kWh. while January, also here, is the worst month where 99% of errors are below 13.5 kWh and 1% are less or equal -6.13 kWh.

In shoulder season the best month of workday model is October with 98% of the errors falling between -4.6 kWh and 5.8 kWh. In contrast April is considered as the worst month where 99% of errors are below 6.6 kWh and 1% are less than -5.8 kWh.

As the workday model, October represents the best month for the weekend model with 98% of errors falling between -3.4 kWh and 4.5 kWh and the worst model is identified in March where 99% of errors are less or equal 8.7 kWh and 1% are less than -3.3 kWh.

Additionally, the forecast errors are biased differently in each month for each model. In our case and according to the mean error metric (ME), we did not observe any clear bias in the four models.

When evaluating the performance of models using the RMSE metric we can say that January has the largest value in winter term for workday and weekend model, with being the hardest month to forecast. However, December and February show the smallest value of RMSE in workday and weekend models respectively, with being the easiest months to forecast.

In shoulder period October has the smallest value for both workday and weekend model with being the easiest month to forecast. Whereas May shows the largest value of RMSE for both workday and weekend models, with being the hardest month to forecast.

(A)

(B)

(C)

(D)

Figure 48. Histogram of the forecast error of the four models using significant calendar data. The forecast error distribution is shown for each month in the year along with 10% and 90% quantiles. The forecast is too high when having a positive error, and too low when having negative error: (A) winter /workdays model, (B) winter / weekend model, (C) shoulder /workdays model, (D) shoulder / weekend model

Table 26. Summary of the hourly forecast error for each month of the four models using significant calendar data. The best month performance is indicated in green, the worst is indicated in red. The quantiles are evaluated in pairs, where the month that have the widest quantile interval is considered the worst.

		RMSE	ME	Error Quantiles (kWh)			
		(kWh)	(kWh)	10%	90%	1%	99%
Winter/ Workdays model	December	1.865	-0.064	-2.238	2.283	-4.079	4.694
	January	3.000	0.055	-2.969	4.092	-5.789	9.702
	February	2.339	0.009	-2.321	2.966	-5.240	6.595
Winter/ Weekends model	December	2.188	-0.521	-3.008	2.491	-4.857	4.430
	January	3.665	0.228	-3.992	4.220	-6.134	13.509
	February	1.959	0.434	-1.771	3.550	-2.601	4.424
Shoulder/ Workdays model	March	2.142	0.384	-1.893	2.935	-4.979	6.408
	April	2.373	0.005	-2.411	3.478	-5.887	6.619
	May	2.359	-0.284	-2.799	2.936	-5.201	5.909
	September	2.322	-0.226	-2.963	2.486	-4.524	6.371
	October	2.029	-0.048	-2.175	2.610	-4.605	5.830
	November	2.099	0.225	-1.954	3.319	-3.564	6.237
Shoulder/ Weekends model	March	2.449	0.594	-1.694	3.749	-3.371	8.713
	April	2.127	0.028	-2.586	2.895	-4.324	5.618
	May	2.542	-0.333	-3.167	2.718	-4.719	6.691
	September	1.766	-0.086	-1.823	2.229	-3.627	4.668
	October	1.589	-0.104	-1.953	1.553	-3.469	4.537
	November	2.311	-0.204	-2.864	2.595	-4.944	6.557

5. DISCUSSION

In this section, we have examined how well did we answer our research questions. As a beginning, we examined to which extent the S-ARX model can characterize the heat load in buildings connected to district heating system, then we explored to which extent the model can predict the heat demand. Furthermore, we discussed the impact of the study on an industry level and finally we highlighted the main threat to validity and the actions that we have taken to tackle these threats.

5.1 Research Question 1. How to characterize the heat load in buildings connected to district heating system?

The S-ARX model was built using multiple linear regression method. The linear regression allows to evaluate the relationship between the criterion variable denoted by the heat load and the predictor variables which represent the components of the model. Using the least square (OLS), the regression coefficients were estimated and yielded an excellent fit for the four models including the workdays and weekends models in both winter and shoulder terms.

Different metrics were used in order to evaluate the goodness of fit. Furthermore, building the S-ARX model with a multiple linear regression approach enabled us to illuminate the supposed linear relationship between the heat load response variable and the predictors (lagged values of heat load, present and lagged values of temperature & irradiation flux and calendar data).

As a matter of fact, the multiple linear relationship enabled to capture the physical dependencies. (Outdoor temperature and irradiation flux), allowed to deal with the energy storage across the data segment using the autoregressive components and enabled to depict the typical and atypical social behaviors in term of heat energy consumption with the use of calendar data. According to their parameter estimates, these calendar data have showed a large influence as good as the outdoor temperature on heat load response variable. Moreover, we have noticed that when increasing the lagged values of the exogenous variables (temperature and irradiation flux), the parameter estimates become less influence on heat load response variable.

5.2 Research Question 2. How to accurately predict the heat demand in buildings connected to district heating system?

5.2.1 Comparison of Models' performance with Different Data Scenarios

As a first step we investigated the inclusion of various type of input parameters for the four models. Indeed, three data scenarios have been presented "lagged heat load", "lagged weather data" and "calendar data". The results of model comparison with different data scenario have shown that the inclusion of lagged weather data and calendar data have improved the performance of the models in term of prediction accuracy.

In this respect, the heat demand seemed to depend strongly on weather data in which the temperature was the most important explanatory variable when modelling the district heating load. Moreover, the irradiation flux can also be a significant variable for the heat load. The calendar data were added as input to variables to better capture the consumer behavior, as a result, the reduction in the errors was very small compared to the lagged weather data.

In winter, the models have shown the highest value of RMSE and MAE compared to models in shoulder terms since the latter have shown a less varying profile when it comes to heat energy consumption.

5.2.2 Seasonal Performance Variation

In a second step and according to the previous results we decided to select the 3rd data scenario which include lagged heat load, lagged weather data and calendar data. The aforementioned models were evaluated, in this connection, the variation of the forecasting error with the time of the days has been investigated for each model.

Interestingly, we have noticed that for most of the hours in April, May and more or less in September, the model tremendously failed to predict the heat demand. Usually, these months are known to have high external temperature. However, at some moments low temperatures can be identified. As consequence, the monitored heat energy consumption does not correspond to this unexpected climatic condition. This divergence could be explained by a reduction of heat load by the district heating operator in this week.

According to the distribution of forecast errors for each month in the year in along with error quantiles, the results have shown that December has performed the best for the workdays

model in winter term with the lowest RMSE value among other months in that period. In contrast January has been the worst month in forecasting with having the highest value of RMSE. In weekend model, February has been considered as the best month for heat demand prediction contrarily to January which also has been the worst in this period. October was the best month for accurate forecasting in shoulder terms for both workdays and weekend models. However, in may the performance of the forecasting model was very low.

5.3 Impact of the study on industry

The presented model can be used for different purposes. On the one hand, it provides insight into the heat demand characterization for the whole district heating system in order to better optimize its production level. Furthermore, it can be exploited to model individual buildings' demand and explore the heat load pattern in each dwelling.

As a matter of fact, the estimation for a range of buildings with different heat load profiles helps to optimize the resources of heat generation both in primary energy and economic savings. By virtue to its simplicity and clearness, the model enables the identification for both domestic hot water (DHW) and space heating (SH).

5.4 Validity Threats

From a research design point of view, threats to validity can occur when a researcher, for instance, test a hypothesis in a manner other than he intended. [\[25\]](#) In this part three matters of validity will be discussed.

5.4.1 Internal Validity

In our present research, the internal validity was based on two level. First, we present the threats to internal validity for the overall study. Second, we look into this threat from another perspective when we have assessed the multiple linear regression.

History

Refers to unrelated event that influence the outcome. [\[26\]](#) In our case study, the data gaps resulted in having a huge load in the first hour after the data recovery which indicate the integral value of the delivered energy for the full period data loss. To avoid this problem, we removed the heat that have huge load and treat them as a missing value. After performing

the outlier detection process the imputation of missing values an imputation process has been executed by filling the heat load missing value by the average from the same hour taken from the rest of the data.

Experimental Mortality

Experimental Mortality indicate the loss of subjects, meaning dropping out of experiments prior to completion [27]. In our case study, bad data were identified from experiment. They may have not run-in proper way. These data are considered as outliers. As a result, the removal of these values is necessary as they have large impact on the regression.

With the aim of making the normality assumption valid. We have divided the data into subsets of temperatures. In each of these subsets we have applied an outlier removal process using the Interquartile Range (IQR) method.

Threats To Internal Validity of Multiple Linear Regression: Omitted Variable Bias and Wrong Functional Form

The Omitted Variable Bias and the Wrong Functional Form happen when a linear regression model is not correctly specified in a study. In this connection the bias can occur when important variables, which are significant, are omitted[28].

In our study, the night setback was identified, where the heat demand is reduced. Therefore, the heat energy consumption pattern differs along different hours independently from climatic variables. That is why we have decided to incorporate a time dependency variable, which was represented by the calendar data. The aforementioned variables have been included as dummy variables. Indeed, along with holiday data, the calendar data were represented as categorical with binary variables (0 or 1). Each hour of the full week (168 h) has been encoded. For example, the first hour of Monday is encoded (01:00), second hour (Monday 02:00) and etc.

5.4.2 External Validity

External validity is to produce general knowledge about the real world and apply our findings in a broader context.[29]

At the beginning of the study, among 42 buildings connected to district heating system, we have selected one residential apartment building. To address the complexity of seasonality in heat load forecasting, we chose to apply the modelling process on full year data and winter

data separately. Also, we excluded the summer term due divergence and poor correlation with climatic variables. However, in other buildings connected to district heating system, we have identified that there is no occupation on weekends such as office and school buildings.

Since our goal is to construct a heat load forecasting model applicable for all buildings connected to district heating, we decided to recalibrate our model in order to address the weekly seasonality. Hence, we have provided four models: two models for winter (workdays and weekend model) and two models for shoulder term (workdays and weekend model).

5.4.3 Construct Validity: Training/Testing Errors

In the present study, the dataset was split into training and testing set. For the purpose of avoiding having different consumption patterns in each set, the division process accrued on monthly basis.

For instance, in winter term, December and January data were taken as training set and February was taken as testing set. Similar method has been applied in shoulder term where March, April and September were represented as training data and May, October and November as testing data. Nevertheless, the evaluation metrics' results such as the mean absolute error (MAE) and root mean square error (RMSE) were unsound. Essentially, the training errors values were higher than the testing errors. Indeed, this behavior occurs when the training sets has many hard cases to learn.

Therefore, we decided to change our training/testing approach. In this respect, the splitting process was performed in a way that the learning data and testing data coincide with all different heat consumption patterns with the respect of the season of the year. The training and testing data have been defined in a daily basis. The odd days have been defined as training set and the even days have been defined as testing set. Consequently, we were able to obtain reasonable results.

6. CONCLUSION

We have presented a data driven model for the characterization and prediction of heat demand in buildings connected to district heating (DH) networks. Our new model is applied in a short-term heat load forecast with high temporal resolution (hourly and daily timestamp) for different buildings relying on weather and calendar information.

The heat load patterns are investigated using multi step forecasting model based on Segmented Autoregressive model with exogenous variables combined with multiple linear regression (S-ARX-MLR). It is able to handle linear dynamic relationship of system parameters reliably. Consequently, we can get a robust and accurate regression model used in time series forecasting with low calculation and processing cost. Furthermore, S-ARX-MLR enables the incorporation of time dependent consumption patterns represented by the calendar information along with holiday data.

Statistically, the mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) is ranging between 4 to 20 % in winter term, which is considered as an indication that the forecast is acceptably accurate. Whereas, in shoulder term the MAPE is ranging between 20 to 80% which is considered as an indication that the forecast is low. The models in winter and shoulder term show a good performance in predicting the heat demand in early morning of the days. Having such estimation available for different buildings in district heating networks help to optimize the resource for heat generation and give rise to both energy and economic savings.

In operational forecast systems, a model with simple and reliable data input may work to make a more robust system. Having several features are not always an advantage to improve the accuracy. For instance, Deep learning (DL) methods doesn't show a great potential in term of heat load forecasting. Nevertheless, future works should inspect different types of models using the deep learning methods to simplify the feature selection procedure and handle multiple inputs variables with noisy dependencies. Hence, make the forecasting process more applicable to a wide range of district heating systems around the world.

REFERENCES

- [1] European Commission. (2016). The roadmap for transforming the EU into a competitive low-carbon economy by 2050 [Online]. Available : https://ec.europa.eu/clima/sites/clima/files/2050_roadmap_en.pdf.
- [2] S. Lettenbichler, J. Corscadden, A. Krasatsenka "Advancing District Heating & Cooling Solutions and Uptake in European Cities," [Online], Sep 30 2020. Available: <https://celsiuscity.eu/>
- [3] Wayback. (2022, Jan. 24). What is Horizon 2020? [Online]. Available : <https://wayback.archive-it.org/12090/20220124080607/https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/what-horizon-2020>
- [4] Cordis. (2022, Oct. 19). Renewable Low Temperature District [Online]. Available : <https://cordis.europa.eu/>
- [5] K. Solanki. (2022, January. 30). What are Research Approaches? | Meaning and Types of Research Approaches [Online]. Available: <https://www.toppers4u.com/2022/01/what-is-research-approaches-meaning-and.html#point1>
- [6] Winston-Salem State University, "Key Elements of a Research Proposal Quantitative Design," [Online]. Available : <https://www.wssu.edu/about/offices-and-departments/office-of-sponsored-programs/pre-award/Files/documents/develop-quantitative.pdf>
- [7] UNIDO, "Energy efficiency in buildings," UNIDO,2009. [Online]. Available: https://www.unido.org/sites/default/files/2009-02/Module18_0.pdf
- [8] S. Oyedepo, E. Anifowose, E. Obembe, S. Khanmohamadi. (2020, November. 6). "Energy-saving strategies on university campus buildings: Covenant University as case study". Energy Services Fundamentals and Financing [Online]. page. 131-154. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-820592-1.00006-3>
- [9] International District Energy Association. (2019). What is District Heating [Online]. Available: <https://www.districtenergy.org/topics/district-heating>
- [10] International District Energy Association. (2019). Why District Heating? [Online]. Available: <https://www.districtenergy.org/topics/district-heating>

- [11] S. Idowu, S. Saguna, C. Ahlund, O. Schelen. "Forecasting Heat Load for Smart District Heating Systems: A Machine Learning Approach," [Online]. Available: <https://www.divaportal.org/smash/get/diva2:1007602/FULLTEXT01.pdf>
- [12] B. Talebi, P. Mirzaei, A. Bastani, F. Haghghat. (2016, October. 4). "A Review of District Heating Systems: Modeling and Optimization". Sec. Sustainable Design and Construction [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fbuil.2016.00022>
- [13] Celsiuscity, "The end-user in the district heating/cooling network," [Online]. Available: https://celsiuscity.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/12/176X_original.pdf
- [14] T.N. Nguyen, T.P. Tran, H.D. Hung, M. Voznak, P.T. Tran, T. Minh, N. Thanh-Long. (2018, November. 9). "Hybrid TSR-PSR Alternate Energy Harvesting Relay Network over Rician Fading Channels: Outage Probability and SER Analysis". Sensors [Online]. vol. 18, issue. 11, page. 3839. Available: <https://doi.org/10.3390/s18113839>
- [15] H.S. Hippert, C.E Pedreira, R.C. Souza. (2001, February). "Neural Networks for Short-Term Load Forecasting: A Review and Evaluation". IEEE TRANSACTIONS ON POWER SYSTEMS [Online]. vol. 16, issue. 1. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/910780>
- [16] J. Page, D. Robinson, J.L. Scartezzini. (2007). "Stochastic Simulation of Occupant Presence and Behaviour in Buildings". Proceedings: Building Simulation [Online]. Available : <https://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/document?repid=rep1&type=pdf&doi=60b9379b5bf299255f8835a68e68f64803cc93cc>
- [17] W. Wang, J. Chen, T. Hong. (2018, July). "Occupancy prediction through machine learning and data fusion of environmental sensing and Wi-Fi sensing in buildings". Automation in Construction 94 (part1) [Online]. Available: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2018.07.007>
- [18] M. Eguizabal, R. Garay, I. Flores. "Simplified model for the short-term forecasting of heat loads in buildings," in Conf. Advances on Clean Energy Research, ICACER 2021, Barcelona, Spain, 2021, pp. 000-000.
- [19] M. Lumbreras, R. Garay, B. Arregi. (2021, October. 6). "Data driven model for heat load prediction in buildings connected to District Heating by using smart heat meters". Energy [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2021.122318>
- [20] G. Gross, F. Galiana. (1987, December). "Short-Term Load Forecasting". Proceedings of the IEEE [Online]. vol. 75, page. 12. Available: <https://gross.ece.illinois.edu/files/2015/03/1987-Dec.pdf>

- [21] T. Fang, R. Lahdelma. (2016, October). "Evaluation of a multiple linear regression model and SARIMA model in forecasting heat demand for district heating system". Applied Energy [Online]. Available: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2016.06.133>
- [22] Kamstrup. Accessed: 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.kamstrup.com/en-en/heat-solutions>
- [23] Gren. Accessed: 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://gren.com>
- [24] University of Tartu, Institute of Physics, Laboratory of Environmental Physics. Accessed: 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://meteo.physic.ut.ee/?lang=en>
- [25] P. Bhandari (2020, May. 1). Internal Validity in Research | Definition, Threats & Examples [Online]. Available: <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/internal-validity/>
- [26] B. Ohlund, C. Yu. Threats to validity of Research Design [Online]. Available: <https://web.pdx.edu/>
- [27] B. Ohlund, C. Yu. Threats to validity of Research Design [Online]. Available: <https://web.pdx.edu/>
- [28] Scholars at Harvard, "Assessing Studies Based on Multiple Regression (SW Ch. 7)," [Online]. Available: <https://scholar.harvard.edu>
- [29] Laerd Dissertation, "Internal validity," [Online], 2012. Available: <https://dissertation.laerd.com/internal-validity.php>
- [30] R.J. Hyndman, G. Athanasopoulos. (2018, April). Forecasting: Principles and Practice [Online]. Available: <https://otexts.com/fpp2/least-squares.html>
- [31] Statistics How To. (2023). Forward Selection: Definition [Online]. Available: <https://www.statisticshowto.com/forward-selection/>
- [32] R.J. Hyndman, G. Athanasopoulos. (2018, April). Forecasting: Principles and Practice [Online]. Available : <https://otexts.com/fpp2/AR.html>

APPENDIX A.

ANN (Artificial Neural Network): A computational model that is used to identify the interrelation of input and output variables based on their predefined activation functions.

FNN (Feedforward Neural Network): A branch of Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), where the connection between the nodes do not form a cycle. This type of model doesn't have a feedback loop in the learning process.

SVM (Support Vector Machine): It is a type of deep learning algorithm. the model solves linear and nonlinear problem. It performs supervised learning for classification or regression of data groups.

KNN (k-Nearest Neighbors Algorithm): It is a supervised learning classifier. The function is only approximated locally in order to make classification or regression.

AR (Autoregressive models): Statistical model that predict future value based on past values. The model measures the correlation between observation at previous time-steps to predict the value of the output.

SARIMA (Seasonal Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average): a straightforward extension of the autoregressive integrated moving average model. the model is useful for modelling seasonal time series.